

APPENDIX 3

Social Data for Health Reference Guide

Use Cases, Data Types,
and Data Services

Authors: Adam Zable, Hannah Chafetz,
Christopher Rosselot, and Stefaan G. Verhulst

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17534968](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17534968)

Table of Contents

Context	2
Demand: Use Cases for Social Data in Health and Wellbeing Research	4
1. Monitoring Health Outcomes and Risks	6
2. Understanding Determinants of Health	32
3. Examining Structural Drivers	43
4. Cross-Cutting Issues	54
Supply: Social Data Sources for Health and Wellbeing Research	63
1. Communication and Social Interaction Data	64
2. Mobility and Geolocation Data	69
3. Health and Wellness Tracking Data	76
4. Environmental and Infrastructure Data	84
5. Financial and Consumption Data	90
6. In-Home and IoT Sensor Data	94
7. Media and Entertainment Data	98
8. Work, Education, and Skill Data	101
Data Services	103

Context

Social data—digital data generated through human interactions with technology platforms, devices, and systems—is becoming an increasingly important resource for understanding and improving health and wellbeing. Researchers are using social data to explore a wide range of questions, from monitoring health outcomes to exploring the social and environmental factors that shape health.

This data takes many forms: structured sensor outputs, unstructured text, behavioral traces, and interaction patterns. It can originate from a variety of domains, including mobility, commerce, communication, home environments, and digital services. In many cases, social data is produced for commercial, operational, or platform-specific purposes. In other cases, it is collected or generated through intentional research efforts or public sector initiatives.

Both the availability of social data and the demand for its use in health research are evolving quickly. Some data types, such as wearable device measurements or social media content, are now well established in health-related research. Others remain underutilized despite growing relevance and potential value. Meanwhile, new and emerging use cases continue to push researchers toward novel forms of social data.

Currently, access to social data for health research is fragmented and inconsistent. There is a substantial asymmetry between the demand for data among researchers and the availability and accessibility of that data from those who control it. In many cases, access must be negotiated on an individual and ad hoc basis, often for one-off projects. Researchers typically lack bargaining power and must navigate complex legal, ethical, and technical hurdles to obtain data.

At the same time, advocates for public-interest research face ongoing challenges in making the case for data sharing. Without a framework that connects emerging research use cases to specific data types, sources, and the existing body of research, it remains difficult to build the sustained partnerships and long-term access that this work requires.

Purpose of the Reference Guide

This Reference Guide serves as an evidence base for the findings and recommendations presented in the report. It brings together both the demand side (how social data is being used in health research) and the supply side (what types of social data are available or emerging), with the goal of making more visible the landscape of current practice and supporting more systematic, sustainable, and responsible use of social data in health research. In doing so, it aims to help foster responsible innovation in the use of social data and to strengthen the impact of health

research on real-world health outcomes.

The Guide also consolidates the full set of case studies and examples we analyzed during the project, including 296 papers identified as meeting our inclusion criteria from a review of several thousand, as detailed in the main report. It also incorporates additional insights gathered through expert consultations, studios, and workshops. By mapping and linking the current landscape of social data types and sources (supply) and the expanding set of health-related use cases (demand), this document is intended to clarify where social data is already being used effectively, where gaps remain, and what kinds of data infrastructure and partnerships could help advance future work.

Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is organized as follows:

1. The first section presents a **taxonomy of use cases** for social data in health and wellbeing research. It outlines how social data is currently being used to support a variety of health research goals, organized into four domains: Health Outcomes and Risks, Determinants of Health, Structural Drivers, and Cross-Cutting Issues. For each research focus area, we provide the complete list of relevant research papers drawn from the literature review conducted for this project, along with the typical types of social data used to support that area of

research.

2. The second section presents a **taxonomy of social data sources**, offering an overview of the types of data currently used—or with strong potential for use—in health-related research. This section categorizes social data across eight domains of sources, and for each data type, provides a concise description, typical actors involved in its collection or access, data structure, privacy considerations, metadata commonly captured, and relevant research focus areas.
3. The third section provides a **mapping of data services**, cataloguing existing services and platforms that are enabling access to social data for health research. For each service, we provide key information including name, location, data types, website, primary functions, funding sources, and notable features.

Demand: Use Cases for Social Data in Health and Wellbeing Research

This section presents the evidence base on how social data is currently being used to support health and wellbeing research. It organizes the full set of papers and use cases identified through our literature review and related sources according to the taxonomy introduced in the main report.

While the taxonomy is explained in detail elsewhere, this section uses it as a framework to map and display the breadth of social data applications across different areas of health research. Each paper or use case—terms we use interchangeably—is assigned to the focus area that best reflects its primary research objective. Where papers could fit under more than one focus area, we selected the most appropriate category to avoid duplication.

Literature Review Parameters

Our review was conducted primarily in March and April 2025, focusing on papers published from 2022 onward. Foundational studies from earlier years were included when relevant. In addition to database searches, we incorporated papers recommended by Advisory Board members, Wellcome Trust partners, studio participants, conference attendees, and expert interviewees.

Searches were conducted across a wide range of journals and databases, including:

OSF Preprints, Nature, Frontiers in Public Health, Preventive Medicine (Elsevier), ACM Digital Library, Journal of Medical Internet Research, arXiv, International Journal of Population Data Science, Social Science & Medicine, and Journal of Health and Social Behavior.

Search terms included (but were not limited to):

non-traditional data, smart data, social data, digital footprint, social media data, app data, wearable data, smartphone data, Internet of Medical Things, sensor data + health, loyalty card data, online search data, mobile phone data, LinkedIn data, Fitbit data, Twitter data, Reddit data, Facebook data, Google, transaction data, shopping data.

Taxonomy Structure

The taxonomy used to classify the use cases is organized into four overarching domains:

1. **Health Outcomes and Risks:** How social data can be used to monitor, predict, or intervene in health outcomes.
2. **Determinants:** How social data helps identify behavioral, social, and environmental factors that influence health.

- 3. **Structural Drivers:** How social data reveals disparities and population-level differences in health.
- 4. **Cross-Domain Issues:** How social data augments broader knowledge systems and addresses ethical, methodological, and technological complexities.

Each domain is further divided into **research themes** and then into more specific **focus areas**. For example:

1. Monitoring Health Outcomes and Risks (domain)

1.1. Health Outcomes and Risk Detection: How social data is used to monitor, predict, or intervene in health outcomes (sub-domain)

1.1.1 Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing (research theme)

A. Depression, Loneliness, and Mental Wellbeing (focus area)

For each focus area, we provide the typical types of social data used in that line of research and a list of relevant papers, with countries of origin, and weblinks included.

Note: While one focus area (3.1.1 - A) centers specifically on LMICs, many other LMIC-led studies appear across different focus areas depending on topic relevance.

1. Monitoring Health Outcomes and Risks

1.1 Health Outcomes and Risk Detection: How social data is used to monitor, predict, or intervene in health outcomes

1.1.1 Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing

A. Depression, Loneliness, and Mental Wellbeing

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Abd-Alrazaq, Alaa, Rawan AlSaad, Farag Shuweihdi, Arfan Ahmed, Sarah Aziz & Javaid Sheikh. **"Systematic review and meta-analysis of performance of wearable artificial intelligence in detecting and predicting depression."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6, no. 84 (2023). Qatar, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00828-5>.
- Niloy Sikder, Lieuwe Verkaar, Anastasiya Paltarzhytskaya, Selin Acan, Elena Krugliakova, Yevgenia Rosenblum, Matthias Krauledat, Martin Dresler, and Paul Zerr, **"Wearanize+: A Multimodal Dataset for Evaluating Wearable Technologies in Sleep Research."** *OSF Preprints*, January 30, 2025. United States. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/dth8y_v1
- Chen, Jie, Ngan Yin Chan, Chun-Tung Li, Joey W. Y. Chan, Yaping Liu, Shirley Xin Li, Steven W. H. Chau, Kwong Sak Leung, Pheng-Ann Heng, Tatia M. C. Lee, Tim M. H. Li & Yun-Kwok Wing. **"Multimodal digital assessment of depression with actigraphy and app in Hong Kong Chinese."** *Translational Psychiatry* 14, no. 150 (2024). Hong Kong SAR, China. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02873-4>.
- Cork, Alicia G., Lukasz Piwek, Laura G. E. Smith, Danaë Stanton Fraser, Adam Joinson, and David A. Ellis. **"The Association Between TikTok and Mental Health: What You See Is More Important Than What You Do."** *PsyArXiv preprint* (2024). United Kingdom. <https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/tm6ku>

- Dai, Ruixuan, Thomas Kannampallil, Jingwen Zhang, Nan Lv, Jun Ma & Chenyang Lu. **"Multi-Task Learning for Randomized Controlled Trials: A Case Study on Predicting Depression with Wearable Data."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 6, no. 2 (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3534591>.
- Das Swain, Vedant, Victor Chen, Shrija Misra, Stephen M. Mattingly, Gregory D. Abowd & Munmun De Choudhury. **"Semantic Gap in Predicting Mental Wellbeing through Passive Sensing."** *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '22)* (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3502037>.
- Das Swain, Vedant, Jingjing Ye, Siva Karthik Ramesh, Abhirup Mondal, Gregory D. Abowd, and Munmun De Choudhury. **"Leveraging Social Media to Predict COVID-19-Induced Disruptions to Mental Well-Being Among University Students: Modeling Study."** *JMIR Formative Research* 8 (2024): e52316. USA. <https://doi.org/10.2196/52316>
- Elmer, Timon, Aurelio Fernández, Marie Stadel, Martien J.H. Kas, and Anna Langener. **"Bidirectional Associations Between Smartphone Usage and Momentary Well-Being in Young Adults: Tackling Methodological Challenges by Combining Experience Sampling Methods with Passive Smartphone Data."** *Emotion* (2024). Spain, The Netherlands, Switzerland. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/uj6df_v1
- Goyal, Abhay, Roger Ho Chun Man, Roy Ka-Wei Lee, Koustuv Saha, Frederick L. Altice, Christian Poellabauer, Orestis Papakyriakopoulos, Lam Yin Cheung, Munmun De Choudhury, Kanica Allagh, and Navin Kumar. **"Using Voice Data to Facilitate Depression Risk Assessment in Primary Health Care."** In *Companion Proceedings of the 16th ACM Web Science Conference (WebSci Companion '24)*, (2024). Germany. United States, Singapore, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630744.3658408>
- Huang, Xiangsheng, Fang Wang, Yuan Gao, Yilong Liao, Wenjing Zhang, Li Zhang, and Zhenrong Xu. **"Depression Recognition Using Voice-Based Pre-Training Model."** *Scientific Reports* 14 (2024): 12734. China. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-024-63556-0>

- Jiang, Yueyi, Yunfan Jiang, Liu Leqi, and Piotr Winkielman. **"Many Ways to Be Lonely: Fine-Grained Characterization of Loneliness and Its Potential Changes in COVID-19."** *Proceedings of the Sixteenth International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media (ICWSM)* (2022). United States.
<https://ojs.aaai.org/index.php/ICWSM/article/view/19302/19074>
- Ji, Xinyu, Taotao Zhan, and Tingshao Zhu. **"Impact of COVID-19 on negative body image: Evidence based on social media data."** *Social Science & Medicine* 340 (2024): 116461. China.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.116461>.
- Jung, Gyeyoung, Soyeon Choi, Yuju Kang & Jaejeung Kim. **"MyListener: An AI-Mediated Journaling Mobile Application for Alleviating Depression and Loneliness Using Contextual Data."** *Companion of the 2024 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing (UbiComp '24)* (2024). South Korea.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3675094.3677601>.
- Kim, Jiyeong, Zhuo Ran Cai, Michael L. Chen, Shawheen J. Rezaei, Sonia Onyeka, Carolyn I. Rodriguez, Tina Hernandez-Boussard, Vladimir Filkov, Rachel A. Whitmer, Eleni Linos, and Yong K. Choi. **"Mental Health Care Needs of Caregivers of People with Alzheimer's Disease from Online Forum Analysis."** *npj Mental Health Research* 3, Article 54. (2024). United States.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s44184-024-00100-y>
- Lengyel, Balázs, Gergő Tóth, Nicholas A. Christakis, and Anikó Bíró. **"Antidepressant Use in Spatial Social Networks."** *Science Advances* 10, no. 49 (2024). Hungary.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adr0302>
- Levinson, Adam Valen, Abhay Goyal, Roger Ho Chun Man, Roy Ka-Wei Lee, Koustuv Saha, Nimay Parekh, Frederick L. Altice, Lam Yin Cheung, Munmun De Choudhury, and Navin Kumar. **"Using Audio Data to Facilitate Depression Risk Assessment in Primary Health Care."** *Preprint, arXiv* (2023). United States, Singapore.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.10928>
- Liziniewicz, Bogna, John Harvey, James Goulding, and Liz Dowthwaite. **"Digital Footprints as Means of Measuring Loneliness Experience and Embeddedness in Social Networks for Designing Digital Mental Health Interventions."** *International Journal of Population Data Science* 9, no. 4 (2024): 13. United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v9i4.2427>

- Matcham, Fiona, Eleanor Carr, Karen M. White, Daniel Leightley, Femke Lamers, Sara Siddi, Pernille Annas, Giovanni de Girolamo, Josep Maria Haro, Matthew Horsfall, Alexandru Ivan, Gemma Lavelle, Qian Li, Francesca Lombardini, David C. Mohr, Vineeth A. Narayan, Brenda W.J.H. Penninx, Claudia Oetzmann, Marc Coromina, Simona K. Simblett, Jens-Christian Weyer, Til Wykes, Spyridon Zorbas, Jan C. Brasen, Inez Myin-Germeys, Pedro Conde, Richard J.B. Dobson, Amos A. Folarin, Yatharth Ranjan, Zinaida Rashid, Nicholas Cummins, James Dineley, Subashini Vairavan, Matthew Hotopf, on behalf of the RADAR-CNS consortium. **"Predictors of engagement with remote sensing technologies for symptom measurement in Major Depressive Disorder."** *Journal of affective disorders*, 310, 106–115 (2022). United Kingdom, Netherlands, Spain, Denmark, Italy, United States, Belgium, Germany.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35525507/>
- Matti Vuorre, Nick Ballou, Thomas Hakman, Kristoffer Magnusson, and Andrew K. Przybylski. **"Affective Uplift During Video Game Play: A Naturalistic Case Study."** *ACM Games* 2, no. 3, Article 23 (2024). United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3659464>
- Matti Vuorre, Niklas Johannes, Kristoffer Magnusson, and Andrew K. Przybylski. **"Time spent playing video games is unlikely to impact well-being."** *Royal Society Open Science* 9, no. 220411 (2022). United Kingdom, Sweden.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.220411>
- Min, Kyungeun, Jeewoo Yoon, Migyeong Kang, Daeun Lee, Eunil Park, and Jinyoung Han. **"Detecting Depression on Video Logs Using Audiovisual Features."** *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 10, Article 788 (2023). South Korea.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-023-02313-6>
- Mow, Jessica L., David E. Gard, Kim T. Mueser, Jasmine Mote, Kathryn Gill, Lawrence Leung, Tairmae Kangarloo & Daniel Fulford. **"Smartphone-based mobility metrics capture daily social motivation and behavior in schizophrenia."** *Schizophrenia Research* 250 (2022). United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2022.09.025>.
- Müller, Sarah and André Bittermann. **"The Emotional Climate of Academia: Exploring Social Media Data as an Indicator of Well-being"** OSF Preprint (2024). Germany.
https://osf.io/preprints/osf/957h8_v2
- Naseem, Usman, Adam G. Dunn, Jinman Kim, and Matloob Khushi. 2022. **"Early Identification of Depression Severity Levels on Reddit Using Ordinal Classification."** *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2022* (2022). United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3485447.3512128>

- Nepal, Subigya, Arvind Pillai, Weichen Wang, Tess Griffin, Amanda C. Collins, Michael Heinz, Damien Lekkas, Shayan Mirjafari, Matthew Nemesure, George Price, Nicholas Jacobson, and Andrew Campbell. 2024. **"MoodCapture: Depression Detection Using In-the-Wild Smartphone Images."** In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '24)*, May 11–16, 2024, USA. ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642680>.
- Owen, David, Amy J. Lynham, Sophie E. Smart, Antonio F. Pardiñas, and Jose Camacho Collados. 2024. **"AI for Analyzing Mental Health Disorders Among Social Media Users: Quarter-Century Narrative Review of Progress and Challenges."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e59225. United Kingdom. <https://www.jmir.org/2024/1/e59225>
- Price, George D., Michael V. Heinz, Seo Ho Song, Matthew D. Nemesure & Nicholas C. Jacobson. **"Using digital phenotyping to capture depression symptom variability: detecting naturalistic variability in depression symptoms across one year using passively collected wearable movement and sleep data."** *Translational Psychiatry* 13, no. 381 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-023-02669-y>.
- Scheuer, Kate, and Ejura Salihu. **"Discussions of Antidepressant Side Effects and Withdrawal on Reddit."** Poster presented at the *International Conference on Quantitative Ethnography (ICQE)* (2021). United States. <https://osf.io/7psfz/download/?format=pdf>
- Shah, Hurmat Ali, and Mowafa Househ. **"Understanding Loneliness Through Analysis of Twitter and Reddit Data: Comparative Study."** *Interactive Journal of Medical Research* 14 (2025): e49464. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/49464>
- Shende, Chinmaey, Soumyashree Sahoo, Stephen Sam, Parit Patel, Reynaldo Morillo, Xinyu Wang, Shweta Ware, Jinbo Bi, Jayesh Kamath, Alexander Russell, Dongjin Song & Bing Wang. **"Predicting Symptom Improvement During Depression Treatment Using Sleep Sensory Data."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 7, no. 3 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3610932>.
- Sinha, Gaurav R., Christopher R. Larrison, Ian Brooks, and Ugur Kursuncu. **"Comparing Naturalistic Mental Health Expressions on Student Loan Debts Big Data."** *OSF Preprint* (2024). United States. https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/qg93e_v1

- Uchiyama, Misa Ashley, Hirofumi Bekki, Tiana McMann, Zhuoran Li, and Tim Mackey. **"Characterizing Experiences With Hikikomori Syndrome on Twitter Among Japanese-Language Users: Qualitative Infodemiology Content Analysis."** *JMIR Infodemiology* 5 (2025). United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/65610>
- Valeri, Linda, Xiaoxuan Cai, Habiballah Rahimi Eichi, Einat Liebenenthal, Scott L. Rauch, Dost Ongur, Russell Schutt, Lisa Dixon, Jukka-Pekka Onnela & Justin Baker. **"Smartphone-based markers of social connectivity in schizophrenia and bipolar disorder."** *NPP – Digital Psychiatry and Neuroscience* (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44277-024-00013-w>.
- Vidal Bustamante, Constanza M., Garth Coombs III, Habiballah Rahimi-Eichi, Patrick Mair, Jukka-Pekka Onnela, Justin T. Baker & Randy L. Buckner. **"Year-Long Digital Phenotyping and Natural Language Processing of Daily Voice Diaries Reveal Affective and Behavioral Signatures of Real-World Life Stress."** *Preprint* (2024). United States. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/fn3aj_v1
- Wang, Weichen, Subigya Nepal, Jeremy F. Huckins, Lessley Hernandez, Vlado Vojdanovski, Dante Mack, Jane Plomp, Arvind Pillai, Mikio Obuchi, Alex daSilva, Ellis Murphy, Elin Hedlund, Courtney Rogers, Meghan Meyer & Andrew Campbell. **"First-Gen Lens: Assessing Mental Health of First-Generation Students across Their First Year at College Using Mobile Sensing."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 6, no. 3 (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543194>.
- Yang, Xingwei, and Guang Li. **"Psychological and Behavioral Insights From Social Media Users: Natural Language Processing-Based Quantitative Study on Mental Well-Being."** *JMIR Formative Research* 9 (2025). United States. <https://formative.jmir.org/2025/1/e60286>.
- Zhang, Tianyi, Shiquan Zhang, Le Fang, Hong Jia, Vassilis Kostakos & Simon D'Alfonso. **"AutoJournaling: A Context-Aware Journaling System Leveraging MLLMs on Smartphone Screenshots."** *Proceedings of the 30th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking (ACM MobiCom '24)* (2024). Australia. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3636534.3698122>.

- Zhang, Tianyi, Songyan Teng, Hong Jia & Simon D'Alfonso. **"Leveraging LLMs to Predict Affective States via Smartphone Sensor Features."** *Companion of the 2024 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing (UbiComp Companion '24)* (2024). Australia. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3675094.3678420>.
- Zhuparris, Ahnjili, Ghobad Maleki, Liesbeth van Londen, Ingrid Koopmans, Vincent Aalten, Iris E. Yocarini, Vasileios Exadaktylos, Albert van Hemert, Adam Cohen, Pim Gal, Robert-Jan Doll, Geert Jan Groeneveld, Gabriël Jacobs & Wessel Kraaij. **"A smartphone- and wearable-based biomarker for the estimation of unipolar depression severity."** *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 18844 (2023). Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-46075-2>.

B. Sleep, Circadian Rhythms, and Mood Dysregulation

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Corponi, Filippo, Bryan M. Li, Gerard Anmella, Ariadna Mas, Isabella Pacchiarotti, Marc Valentí, Iria Grande, Antoni Benabarre, Marina Garriga, Eduard Vieta, Stephen M. Lawrie, Heather C. Whalley, Diego Hidalgo-Mazzei & Antonio Vergari. **"Automated mood disorder symptoms monitoring from multivariate time-series sensory data: getting the full picture beyond a single number."** *Translational Psychiatry* 14, no. 161 (2024). United Kingdom, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02876-1>.

- Corponi, Filippo, Bryan M. Li, Gerard Anmella, Clàudia Valenzuela-Pascual, Ariadna Mas, Isabella Pacchiarotti, Marc Valentí, Iria Grande, Antoni Benabarre, Marina Garriga, Eduard Vieta, Allan H. Young, Stephen M. Lawrie, Heather C. Whalley & Diego Hidalgo-Mazzei. **"Wearable Data From Subjects Playing Super Mario, Taking University Exams, or Performing Physical Exercise Help Detect Acute Mood Disorder Episodes via Self-Supervised Learning: Prospective, Exploratory, Observational Study."** *JMIR Mhealth Uhealth* 12 (2024). United Kingdom, Spain. <https://mhealth.jmir.org/2024/1/e55094>
- Cummins, Jack A., Daniel J. Gottlieb, Tamar Sofer, and Danielle A. Wallace. **"Applying Natural Language Processing Techniques to Map Trends in Insomnia Treatment Terms on the r/Insomnia Subreddit: Infodemiology Study."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e58902. United States. <https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e58902>
- Dworschak, Christine, Thomas Mäder, Charlotta Rühlmann, Andreas Maercker & Birgit Kleim. **"Loneliness and sleep under real-world stress: An intensive longitudinal daily diary and behavioral biomarker study."** *OSF Preprints* (2024). Switzerland. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/fr34j_v1
- Heath, Rachel. **"A Stochastic Multiplicative Cascade Model for Monitoring Relapse in Mood Disorder Using Wearable Data."** *PsyArXiv Preprint* (2024). Australia. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/rdfx9_v1
- Kılıç, Ozan, Berrenur Saylam & Özlem Durmaz İncel. **"Sleep Quality Prediction from Wearables Using Convolution Neural Networks and Ensemble Learning."** *Proceedings of ICMLT 2023: International Conference on Machine Learning Technologies* (2023). Turkey. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.06028>
- Lee, Minki P., Dae Wook Kim, Yu Fang, Ruby Kim, Amy S. B. Bohnert, Srijan Sen & Daniel B. Forger. **"The real-world association between digital markers of circadian disruption and mental health risks."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 355 (2024). United States, South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01348-6>.
- Lim, Dongju, Jaegwon Jeong, Yun Min Song, Chul-Hyun Cho, Ji Won Yeom, Taek Lee, Jung-Been Lee, Heon-Jeong Lee & Jae Kyoung Kim. **"Accurately predicting mood episodes in mood disorder patients using wearable sleep and circadian rhythm features."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 324 (2024). South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01333-z>.

- Willoughby, Adrian R., Iman Alikhani, Mari Karsikas, Xin Yu Chua, and Michael W.L. Chee. "**Country Differences in Nocturnal Sleep Variability: Observations from a Large-Scale, Long-Term Sleep Wearable Study.**" *Sleep Medicine* 110 (October 2023): 155–165. Finland, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2023.08.010>
- Yan, Runze, Xinwen Liu, Janine Dutcher, Michael Tumminia, Daniella Villalba, Sheldon Cohen, David Creswell, Kasey Creswell, Jennifer Mankoff, Anind Dey & Afsaneh Doryab. "**A Computational Framework for Modeling Biobehavioral Rhythms from Mobile and Wearable Data Streams.**" *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology* 13, no. 3 (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3510029>.

C. Suicidal Ideation and Crisis Detection

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Social Media Networks and Architectures

Use Cases

- Ali, Naima Samreen, Sarvech Qadir, Ashwaq Alsoubai, Munmun De Choudhury, Afsaneh Razi, and Pamela J. Wisniewski. "**'I'm gonna KMS:' From Imminent Risk to Youth Joking about Suicide and Self-Harm via Social Media.**" *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '24)*, May 11–16, 2024. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642489>
- Büscher, Rebekka, Tanita Winkler, Jacopo Mocellin, Stephanie Homan, Natasha Josifovski, Marketa Ciharova, Ward van Breda, Sam Kwon, Mark E. Larsen, John Torous, Joseph Firth & Lasse B. Sander. "**A systematic review on passive sensing for the prediction of suicidal thoughts and behaviors.**" *npj Mental Health Research* 3, no. 42 (2024). Germany, Netherlands, Switzerland, Australia, United States, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44184-024-00089-4>

- Dan, Evan, Jianfeng Zhu, and Ruoming Jin. **"Exploring Suicide Factors in Online Discourse: Sentiment and Thematic Analysis of Reddit."** *ACM Transactions on the Web*. (2025). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3716546>
- Patel, Devashru, Steven A. Sumner, Daniel Bowen, Marissa Zwald, Ellen Yard, Jing Wang, Royal Law, Kristin Holland, Theresa Nguyen, Gary Mower, Yushiuan Chen, Jenna Iberg Johnson, Megan Jespersen, Elizabeth Mytty, Jennifer M. Lee, Michael Bauer, Eric Caine, and Munmun De Choudhury. **"Predicting state level suicide fatalities in the United States with realtime data and machine learning."** *npj Mental Health Research* 3 (2024): 3. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44184-023-00045-8>
- Lekkas, Damien, and Nicholas C. Jacobson. **"Breaking the Silence: Leveraging Social Interaction Data to Identify High-Risk Suicide Users Online Using Network Analysis and Machine Learning."** *Scientific Reports* 14, Article 19395 (2024). United States. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-024-70282-0>
- Liu, Xingyun, Miao Liu, Xin Kang, Nuo Han, Yuehan Liao, and Zhihong Ren. **"More Cyberbullying, Less Happiness, and More Injustice—Psychological Changes During the Pericyberbullying Period: Quantitative Study Based on Social Media Data."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. (2024). China. <https://www.jmir.org/2024/1/e57687>
- Pillai, Arvind, Subigya Kumar Nepal, Weichen Wang, Matthew Nemesure, Michael Heinz, George Price, Damien Lekkas, Amanda C. Collins, Tess Griffin, Benjamin Buck, Sarah Masud Preum, Trevor Cohen, Nicholas C. Jacobson, Dror Ben-Zeev & Andrew Campbell. **"Investigating Generalizability of Speech-based Suicidal Ideation Detection Using Mobile Phones."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 7, no. 4 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3631452>.

D. Anxiety, OCD, PTSD, Stress

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Corponi, Filippo, Bryan M. Li, Gerard Anmella, Ariadna Mas, Isabella Pacchiarotti, Marc Valentí, Iria Grande, Antoni Benabarre, Marina Garriga, Eduard Vieta, Stephen M. Lawrie, Heather C. Whalley, Diego Hidalgo-Mazzei & Antonio Vergari. **"Automated mood disorder symptoms monitoring from multivariate time-series sensory data: getting the full picture beyond a single number."** *Translational Psychiatry* 14, no. 161 (2024). United Kingdom, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02876-1>.
- Corponi, Filippo, Bryan M. Li, Gerard Anmella, Clàudia Valenzuela-Pascual, Ariadna Mas, Isabella Pacchiarotti, Marc Valentí, Iria Grande, Antoni Benabarre, Marina Garriga, Eduard Vieta, Allan H. Young, Stephen M. Lawrie, Heather C. Whalley & Diego Hidalgo-Mazzei. **"Wearable Data From Subjects Playing Super Mario, Taking University Exams, or Performing Physical Exercise Help Detect Acute Mood Disorder Episodes via Self-Supervised Learning: Prospective, Exploratory, Observational Study."** *JMIR Mhealth Uhealth* 12 (2024). United Kingdom, Spain. <https://mhealth.imir.org/2024/1/e55094>
- Cummins, Jack A., Daniel J. Gottlieb, Tamar Sofer, and Danielle A. Wallace. **"Applying Natural Language Processing Techniques to Map Trends in Insomnia Treatment Terms on the r/Insomnia Subreddit: Infodemiology Study."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e58902. United States. <https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e58902>
- Dworschak, Christine, Thomas Mäder, Charlotta Rühlmann, Andreas Maercker & Birgit Kleim. **"Loneliness and sleep under real-world stress: An intensive longitudinal daily diary and behavioral biomarker study."** *OSF Preprints* (2024). Switzerland. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/fr34j_v1
- Heath, Rachel. **"A Stochastic Multiplicative Cascade Model for Monitoring Relapse in Mood Disorder Using Wearable Data."** *PsyArXiv Preprint* (2024). Australia. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/rdfx9_v1
- Kılıç, Ozan, Berrenur Saylam & Özlem Durmaz İncel. **"Sleep Quality Prediction from Wearables Using Convolution Neural Networks and Ensemble Learning."** *Proceedings of ICMLT 2023: International Conference on Machine Learning Technologies* (2023). Turkey. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.06028>

- Lee, Minki P., Dae Wook Kim, Yu Fang, Ruby Kim, Amy S. B. Bohnert, Srijan Sen & Daniel B. Forger. **"The real-world association between digital markers of circadian disruption and mental health risks."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 355 (2024). United States, South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01348-6>.
- Lim, Dongju, Jaegwon Jeong, Yun Min Song, Chul-Hyun Cho, Ji Won Yeom, Taek Lee, Jung-Been Lee, Heon-Jeong Lee & Jae Kyoung Kim. **"Accurately predicting mood episodes in mood disorder patients using wearable sleep and circadian rhythm features."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 324 (2024). South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01333-z>.
- Willoughby, Adrian R., Iman Alikhani, Mari Karsikas, Xin Yu Chua, and Michael W.L. Chee. **"Country Differences in Nocturnal Sleep Variability: Observations from a Large-Scale, Long-Term Sleep Wearable Study."** *Sleep Medicine* 110 (October 2023): 155–165. Finland, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2023.08.010>
- Yan, Runze, Xinwen Liu, Janine Dutcher, Michael Tumminia, Daniella Villalba, Sheldon Cohen, David Creswell, Kasey Creswell, Jennifer Mankoff, Anind Dey & Afsaneh Doryab. **"A Computational Framework for Modeling Biobehavioral Rhythms from Mobile and Wearable Data Streams."** *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology* 13, no. 3 (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3510029>.

E. Cognitive Aging, Dementia, Neurodegenerative Conditions

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Bennett, Casey C., Mindy K. Ross, EuGene Baek, Dohyeon Kim & Alex D. Leow. **"Smartphone accelerometer data as a proxy for clinical data in modeling of bipolar disorder symptom trajectory."** *npj Digital Medicine* 5, no. 181 (2022). United States and South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00741-3>.
- Khan, Shehroz S., Pratik K. Mishra, Bing Ye, Smit Patel, Kristine Newman, Alex Mihailidis & Andrea Iaboni. **"A Novel Multi-Modal Sensor Dataset and Benchmark to Detect Agitation in People Living with Dementia in a Residential Care Setting."** *ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare* 6, no. 3 (2025). Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3720550>.

- Muurling, Marijn, Casper de Boer, Srinivasan Vairavan, Robbert L. Harms, Antonella Santucci Chadha, Ioannis Tarnanas, Estefania Vilarino Luis, Dorota Religa, Martha Therese Gjesten, Samantha Galluzzi, Marta Ibarria Sala, Ivan Koychev, Lucrezia Hausner, Mara Gkioka, Dag Aarsland, Pieter Jelle Visser & Anna-Katharine Brem. **"Augmented reality versus standard tests to assess cognition and function in early Alzheimer's disease."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6, no. 234 (2023). Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00978-6>.
- Ning, Emma, Andrea Cladek, Mindy K. Ross, Sarah Kabir, Amruta Barve, Ellyn Kennelly, Faraz Hussain, Jennifer Duffecy, Scott L. Langenecker, Theresa Nguyen, Theja Tulabandhula, John Zulueta, Olusola Ajilore, Alexander P. Demos & Alex Leow. **"Smartphone-derived virtual keyboard dynamics coupled with accelerometer data as a window into understanding brain health."** *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3580906>
- Peterson, Colleen, Renée M. St. Louis, and Carol A. Flannagan. **"Enhancing Enrollment and Adherence in Long-term Wearables Dementia Research: A Qualitative Synthesis from a Systematic Review."** *JMIR Aging* (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/preprints.63768>

- Rosická, Anna Marie, Vanessa Teckentrup, Sol Fittipaldi, Agustin Ibanez, Andrew Pringle, Eoghan Gallagher, Anna Kathleen Hanlon, Nathalie Claus, Cathal McCrory, Brian Lawlor, Lorina Naci & Claire M. Gillan. **"Modifiable dementia risk factors associated with objective and subjective cognition."** *Alzheimer's & Dementia* 20 (2024). Ireland, Chile, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13885>.

F. ADHD and Behavioral Disorders

Typical Data Types

- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Media Content Consumption Data
- Crowdsourced Media Content and Annotations
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Jaiswal, Aditi, Ruben Kruiper, Abdur Rasool, Aayush Nandkeolyar, Dennis P. Wall & Peter Washington. **"Digitally Diagnosing Multiple Developmental Delays Using Crowdsourcing Fused With Machine Learning: Protocol for a Human-in-the-Loop Machine Learning Study."** *JMIR Research Protocols* 13 (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/52205>.

- Monfared, Tahami, Amir Abbas, Yaakov Stern, Stephen Doogan, Michael Irizarry, and Quanwu Zhang. **"Understanding Barriers Along the Patient Journey in Alzheimer's Disease Using Social Media Data."** *Neurology and Therapy* 12 (2023): 899–918. United States and Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40120-023-00472-x>

1.1.2 Chronic Disease Monitoring and Management

A. Cardiovascular and Blood Pressure Monitoring

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- In-Home IoT Device Data
- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

Use Cases

- Barry, Colin, Tatsuo Kumamoto, Amparo Averbuj, and Edward Jay Wang. **"VibroBP: An Oscillometric Smartphone Blood Pressure App."** In *Companion of the 2024 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing (UbiComp Companion '24)*, (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3675094.3677552>

- Keys, Rachel, Paul Marshall, Graham Stuart, and Aisling Ann O'Kane. **"I think it saved me. I think it saved my heart": The Complex Journey From Self-Tracking With Wearables To Diagnosis.** *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '24)* (2024). United States, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642701>
- Liu, Ivan, Fangyuan Liu, Qi Zhong, and Shiguang Ni. **"A Finger on the Pulse of Cardiovascular Health: Estimating Blood Pressure with Smartphone Photoplethysmography-Based Pulse Waveform Analysis."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.11117v3* (2024). China. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.11117>
- Nazaret, Achille, Sana Tonekaboni, Gregory Darnell, Shirley You Ren, Guillermo Sapiro, and Andrew C. Miller. **"Modeling personalized heart rate response to exercise and environmental factors with wearables data."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6 (2023): 207. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00926-4>
- Rahman, Md. Obaidur, Mohammad Abul Kashem, Al-Akhir Nayan, Most. Fahmida Akter, Fazly Rabbi, Marzia Ahmed & Mohammad Asaduzzaman. **"Internet of Things (IoT) based ECG System for Rural Health Care."** *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications* 12, no. 6 (2021). Bangladesh. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.02226>

- Reddy, C. Rajashekar, Vivian Dsouza, Ashok Samraj Thangarajan, Przemysław Pawełczak, Fahim Kawsar, and Alessandro Montanari. **"BioPulse: Towards enabling perpetual vital signs monitoring using a body patch."** *Proceedings of the 26th International Workshop on Mobile Computing Systems and Applications (HotMobile '25)* (2025). United States..
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3708468.3711891>
- Scholte, Niels T. B., Annemiek E. van Ravensberg, Abdul Shakoor, Eric Boersma, Eelko Ronner, Rudolf A. de Boer, Jasper J. Brugts, Nico Bruining, and Robert M. A. van der Boon. **"A scoping review on advancements in noninvasive wearable technology for heart failure management."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7 (2024): 279. Netherlands.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01268-5>
- Umer, Muhammad, Turki Aljrees, Hanen Karamti, Abid Ishaq, Shtwai Alsubai, Marwan Omar, Ali Kashif Bashir, and Imran Ashraf. **"Heart failure patients monitoring using IoT-based remote monitoring system."** *Scientific Reports* 13 (2023): 19213. Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, United States, United Kingdom, India, Lebanon, South Korea.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-46322-6>

B. Obesity, Diabetes, and Metabolic Health

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- Shopping Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Baker, Wirtz, Julia Mariel, Sonia Alejandra Pou, Camila Niclis, Eugenia Haluszka, and Laura Rosana Aballay. **"Non-traditional data sources in obesity research: a systematic review of their use in the study of obesogenic environments."** *International Journal of Obesity* 47 (2023): 686–696. Argentina.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1038/s41366-023-01331-3>
- Kiss, Orsolya, Fiona C. Baker, Robert Palovics, Erin E. Dooley, Kelley Pettee Gabriel, and Jason M. Nagata. **"Using explainable machine learning and Fitbit data to investigate predictors of adolescent obesity."** *Scientific Reports* 14 (2024): 12563. United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-60811-2>

- Nagpal, Meghan, Niloofar Jalali, Diana Sherifali, Plinio Morita, and Joseph A. Cafazzo. **"Investigating Reddit Data on Type 2 Diabetes Management During the COVID-19 Pandemic Using Latent Dirichlet Allocation Topic Modeling and Valence Aware Dictionary for Sentiment Reasoning Analysis: Content Analysis."** *JMIR Formative Research* 9 (2025). United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/51154>
- Sørensen, Kathrine Kold, Emilie Prang Nielsen, Amalie Lykkemark Møller, Mikkel Porsborg Andersen, Frederik Trier Møller, Mads Melbye, Miriam Kolko, et al. **"Food Purchases in Households with and without Diabetes Based on Consumer Purchase Data."** *Preventing Chronic Disease* 19 (2022). Denmark. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcd.2022.04.001>.
- Zahedani, Ashkan Dehghani, Tracey McLaughlin, Arvind Veluvali, Nima Aghaeepour, Amir Hosseinian, Saransh Agarwal, Jingyi Ruan, Shital Tripathi, Mark Woodward, Noosheen Hashemi, and Michael Snyder. **"Digital health application integrating wearable data and behavioral patterns improves metabolic health."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6 (2023): 216. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00956-y>

C. Other Chronic Conditions

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- Shopping Data

Use Cases

- Brewer, Hannah R., Yasemin Hirst, Marc Chadeau-Hyam, Eric Johnson, Sudha Sundar, and James M. Flanagan. **"Association Between Purchase of Over-the-Counter Medications and Ovarian Cancer Diagnosis in the Cancer Loyalty Card Study (CLOCS): Observational Case-Control Study."** *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance* 9 (2023): e41762. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.2196/41762>
- Griffin, Ashley C., Lucas Mentch, Feng-Chang Lin, and Arlene E. Chung. **"mHealth Physical Activity and Patient-Reported Outcomes in Patients With Inflammatory Bowel Diseases: Cluster Analysis."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e48020. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/48020>

- Doshi, Krupa B., Seong Hyun Moon, Michael D. Whitaker, and Thurmon E. Lockhart. **"Assessment of gait and posture characteristics using a smartphone wearable system for persons with osteoporosis with and without falls."** *Scientific Reports* 13 (2023): 538. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-27788-w>
- Gagnon, Marie-Pierre, Steven Ouellet, Eugène Attisso, Wilfried Supper, Samira Amil, Caroline Rhéaume, Jean-Sébastien Paquette, Christian Chabot, Marie-Claude Laferrière, and Maxime Sasseville. **"Wearable Devices for Supporting Chronic Disease Self-Management: Scoping Review."** *Interactive Journal of Medical Research* 13 (2024): e55925. Canada. <https://doi.org/10.2196/55925>
- Ogundare, Oluwatosin, and Subuola Sofolahan. **"Large Language Models in Ambulatory Devices for Home Health Diagnostics: A case study of Sickle Cell Anemia Management."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.03715v1* (2023). Nigeria and United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.03715>
- Poon, Neo, Claire Haworth, Elizabeth Dolan, and Anya Skatova. **"Studying Health and Illness Experience Using Linked Data (SHIELD): Empowering Customers to Donate Shopping Data for Chronic Pain Research."** *International Journal of Population Data Science* 9, no. 4 (2024): 06. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v9i4.2420>

D. Respiratory Conditions

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- In-Home IoT Device Data
- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

Use Cases

- Dolan, Elizabeth, James Goulding, Harry Marshall, Gavin Smith, Gavin Long, and Laila J. Tata. **"Assessing the value of integrating national longitudinal shopping data into respiratory disease forecasting models."** *Nature Communications* 14, no. 7258 (2023). England. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42776-4>
- Radin, Jennifer M., Julia Moore Vogel, Felipe Delgado, Erin Coughlin, Matteo Gadaleta, Jay A. Pandit & Steven R. Steinhubl. **"Long-term changes in wearable sensor data in people with and without Long COVID."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 246 (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01238-x>

- Rafa, Nafisa Shamim, Basma Binte Azmal, Abdur Rab Dhruba, Mohammad Monirujjaman Khan, Turki M. Alanazi, Faris A. Almalki & Othman AlOmeir. **"IoT-Based Remote Health Monitoring System Employing Smart Sensors for Asthma Patients during COVID-19 Pandemic."** *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing* (2022). Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.06511>

E. Neurological Conditions

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Use Cases

- Adams, Jamie L., Tairmae Kangarloo, Brian Tracey, Patricio O'Donnell, Dmitri Volfson, Robert D. Latzman, Neta Zach, Robert Alexander, Peter Bergethon, Joshua Cosman, David Anderson, Allen Best, Joan Severson, Melissa A. Kostrzebski, Peggy Auinger, Peter Wilmot, Yvonne Pohlson, Emma Waddell, Stella Jensen-Roberts, Yishu Gong, Krishna Praneeth Kilambi, Teresa Ruiz Herrero, E. Ray Dorsey & the Parkinson Study Group Watch-PD Study Investigators and Collaborators. **"Using a smartwatch and smartphone to assess early Parkinson's disease in the WATCH-PD study."** *npj Parkinson's Disease* 9 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-023-00497-x>.
- Aziz, Abdul, Nhat Pham, Neel Vora, Cody Reynolds, Jaime Lehnen, Pooja Venkatesh, Zhuoran Yao, Jay Harvey, Tam Vu, Kan Ding & Phuc Nguyen. **"An Unobtrusive and Lightweight Ear-worn System for Continuous Epileptic Seizure Detection."** *ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare* 6, no. 1 (2025). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3703164>.
- Bhagubai, Miguel, Christos Chatzichristos, Lauren Swinnen, Jaiver Macea, Jingwei Zhang, Lieven Lagae, Katrien Jansen, Andreas Schulze-Bonhage, Francisco Sales, Benno Mahler, Yvonne Weber, Wim Van Paesschen & Maarten De Vos. **"SeizelT2: Wearable Dataset of Patients with Focal Epilepsy."** *Preprint* (2025). Belgium, Germany, Portugal, Sweden. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.01224>

- Gashi, Shkurta, Pietro Oldrati, Max Moebus, Marc Hilty, Liliana Barrios, Firat Ozdemir, Veronika Kana, Andreas Lutterotti, Gunnar Rättsch & Christian Holz. **"Modeling multiple sclerosis using mobile and wearable sensor data."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 64 (2024). Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01025-8>
- Johnson, Stephen A., Marta Karas, Katherine M. Burke, Marcin Strackiewicz, Zoe A. Scheier, Alison P. Clark, Satoshi Iwasaki, Amir Lahav, Amrita S. Iyer, Jukka-Pekka Onnela, and James D. Berry. **"Wearable device and smartphone data quantify ALS progression and may provide novel outcome measures."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6 (2023): 34. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00778-y>
- Mao, Junqi, Puen Zhou, Xiaoyao Wang, Hongbo Yao, Liuyang Liang, Yiqiao Zhao, Jiawei Zhang, Dayan Ban & Haiwu Zheng. **"A Health Monitoring System Based on Flexible Triboelectric Sensors for Intelligence Medical Internet of Things and Its Applications in Virtual Reality."** *Preprint* (2024). China, Canada. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.07185>
- Parisi, Federico, Giulia Corniani, Paolo Bonato, David Balkwill, Patrick Acuna, Criscely Go, Nutan Sharma & Christopher D. Stephen. **"Motor assessment of X-linked dystonia parkinsonism via machine-learning-based analysis of wearable sensor data."** *Scientific Reports* 14 (2024). United States, Philippines. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-63946-4>
- Rashid, Zulqarnain, Akash Roy Choudhury, Amos A. Folarin, Yatharth Ranjan, Pauline Conde, Heet Sankesara, Elisa Bruno & Richard J. B. Dobson. **"Remote Monitoring of Epilepsy Patients with Wearable Device and Smartphone."** *Companion of the 2024 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing (UbiComp '24)* (2024). United Kingdom, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3675094.3677592>.
- Visser, Marjolein, Verena Schoser, Heather Wilson, Heidi T. M. Sinke, Philip G. L. Morrison, Cornelis H. Slieker, Aline van der Holst, Mayke A. Oosterhof, Luc J. W. Evers, Bastiaan R. Bloem & Rick C. Helmich. **"Digital biomarkers for non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease: the state of the art."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 186 (2024). Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01144-2>.

F. Post-Surgical Recovery and Rehabilitation

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Use Cases

- Xu, Ziqi, Jingwen Zhang, Jacob Greenberg, Madelyn Frumkin, Saad Javeed, Justin K. Zhang, Braeden Benedict, Kathleen Botterbush, Thomas L. Rodebaugh, Wilson Z. Ray, and Chenyang Lu. "**Predicting multi-dimensional surgical outcomes with multi-modal mobile sensing: A case study with patients undergoing lumbar spine surgery.**" *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 8, no. 2 (2024): 81. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3659628>
- Zhang, Jingwen, Dingwen Li, Ruixuan Dai, Heidy Cos, Gregory A. Williams, Lacey Raper, Chet W. Hammill, and Chenyang Lu. "**Predicting surgical outcomes using wearables.**" *GetMobile: Mobile Computing and Communications* 28, no. 2 (2024): 17–22. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3686138.3686146>.
- Zhang, Jingwen, Dingwen Li, Ruixuan Dai, Heidy Cos, Gregory A. Williams, Lacey Raper, Chet W. Hammill, and Chenyang Lu. "**Predicting Post-Operative Complications with Wearables: A Case Study with Patients Undergoing Pancreatic Surgery.**" *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 6, no. 2 (2022): 87. United States. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3534578>

1.1.3 Substance Use, Addictions, and Behavioral Risk

A. Tobacco, Alcohol, and Drug Use Detection

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Use Cases

- Giorgi, Salvatore, David B. Yaden, Johannes C. Eichstaedt, Lyle H. Ungar, H. Andrew Schwartz, Amy Kwarteng, and Brenda Curtis. "**Predicting U.S. County Opioid Poisoning Mortality from Multi-Modal Social Media and Psychological Self-Report Data.**" *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 9027 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-34468-2>
- Joshi, Aditya, Diego Federico Kaune, Phillip Leff, Emily Fraser, Sarah Lee, Morgan Harrison, and Moustafa Hazin. "**Self-Reported Side Effects Associated With Selective Androgen Receptor Modulators: Social Media Data Analysis.**" *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e65031. United States. <https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e65031>

- Kierstead, Elexis, Nathan Silver, and Michael Amato. "Examining Quitting Experiences on Quit Vaping Subreddits From 2015 to 2021: Content Analysis." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e52129. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/52129>
- Lee, Hayeon, Ahreum Kim, Seungwoo Bae, and Uichin Lee. "S-ADL: Exploring Smartphone-based Activities of Daily Living to Detect Blood Alcohol Concentration in a Controlled Environment." *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '24)*, 2024. Republic of Korea. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642832>
- ŌURA. "Oura Research: Identifying Opioid Use Disorder with Continuous Health Monitoring." *ŌURA Blog*, April 25, 2024. United States. <https://ouraring.com/blog/oura-research-opioid-us-e-disorder/#:~:text=Using%20continuous%20health%20monitoring%20from,physical%20inactivity%20C%20and%20physiological%20stress>

B. Relapse Prediction and Intervention

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data

Use Cases

- Perski, Olga, Deepak Kale, Colleen Leppin, Tomi Okpako, Daniel Simons, Sarah P. Goldstein, Charlotte N. Ōverup, and Jamie Brown. "Supervised machine learning to predict smoking lapses from Ecological Momentary Assessments and sensor data: Implications for just-in-time adaptive intervention development." *PLOS Digital Health* 3, no. 8 (2024): e0000594. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000594>
- Perski, Olga, Kezhi Li, Nikolas Pontikos, David Simons, Stephanie P. Goldstein, Felix Naughton, and Jamie Brown. "Classification of Lapses in Smokers Attempting to Stop: A Supervised Machine Learning Approach Using Data From a Popular Smoking Cessation Smartphone App." *Nicotine & Tobacco Research* 25, no. 7 (2023): 1330–1339. United Kingdom and United States. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntad051>

1.1.4 Infectious Disease Surveillance and Outbreak Response

A. Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data
- Water and Wastewater Sensor Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Online Search Behavior
- Platform-Based Aggregated Mobility Data
- Shopping Data
- News Media and News Content Data
- Geospatial Datasets

Use Cases

- Aldosery, Aisha, Dinarte Vasconcelos, Miguel Ribeiro, Nuno Nunes, and Patty Kostkova. **"Mosquito Ovitrap IoT Sensing System (MOISS): Internet of Things-based System for Continuous, Real-Time and Autonomous Environment Monitoring."** In *Proceedings of the 2022 IEEE 8th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*, Yokohama, 26 October–11 November 2022. Portugal.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/WF-IoT54382.2022.10152111>
- Arifi, Dorian, Bernd Resch, Mauricio Santillana, Weihe Wendy Guan, Steffen Knoblauch, Sven Lautenbach, Thomas Jaenisch, Ivonne Morales, and Clemens Havas. **"Geosocial Media's Early Warning Capabilities Across US County-Level Political Clusters: Observational Study."** *JMIR Infodemiology* 5 (2025). Austria.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/58539>
- Ascione, Claudio, and Eugenio Valdano. **"How Floods May Affect the Spatial Spread of Respiratory Pathogens: The Case of Emilia-Romagna, Italy in May 2023."** *medRxiv preprint*, September 23, 2024. Italy, France.
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.20.24314056>

- Athanasiou, Maria, Georgios Fragkozidis, Konstantia Zarkogianni, and Konstantina S. Nikita. **"Long Short-term Memory–Based Prediction of the Spread of Influenza-Like Illness Leveraging Surveillance, Weather, and Twitter Data: Model Development and Validation."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 25 (2023): e42519. Greece. <https://doi.org/10.2196/42519>
- Babanejaddehaki, Ghazaleh, Aijun An, and Manos Papagelis. **"Disease Outbreak Detection and Forecasting: A Review of Methods and Data Sources."** *ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare* 6, no. 2 (2025): Article 13. Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708549>
- Bolt, Kaylin, Diana Gil-González, and Nuria Oliver. **"Unconventional Data, Unprecedented Insights: Leveraging Non-Traditional Data During a Pandemic."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024): 1350743. Spain, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1350743>
- Dolan, Elizabeth, James Goulding, Alexandra R. Lang, Laila J. Tata, and Anya Skatova. **"The Feasibility of Using Individual-Level Loyalty Card Data for Disease Surveillance: A Pilot Study on COVID-19."** *Research Square preprint*, posted October 14, 2024. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5239099/v1>
- Dougherty, Peter Erdmann, Frederik Trier Møller, Steen Ethelberg, Gunnar Øyvind Isaksson Rø, and Solveig Jore. **"Simulation and Identification of Foodborne Outbreaks in a Large Supermarket Consumer Purchase Dataset."** *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 11491 (2022). Norway. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-15584-x>
- Guo, Muzhe, Yong Ma, Efe Eworuke, Melissa Khashei, Jaejoon Song, Yueqin Zhao, and Fang Jin. **"Identifying COVID-19 Cases and Extracting Patient-Reported Symptoms From Reddit Using Natural Language Processing."** *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 13721 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39986-7>
- Kelley, Kathleen, Nicolò Gozzi, Mattia Mazzoli, and Daniela Paolotti. **"Exploring Influenza Vaccination Determinants through Digital Participatory Surveillance."** *BMC Public Health* 25, no. 1345 (2025). Italy. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-025-22496-8>.

- Keshaviah, Aparna, Ian Huff, Xindi C. Hu, Virginia Guidry, Ariel Christensen, Steven Berkowitz, Stacie Reckling, Rachel T. Noble, Thomas Clerkin, Denene Blackwood, Sandra L. McLellan, Adélaïde Roguet, and Isabel Musse. **"Separating Signal from Noise in Wastewater Data: An Algorithm to Identify Community-Level COVID-19 Surges in Real Time."** *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120, no. 31 (2023): e2216021120. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216021120>
- Keshaviah, Aparna, Megan B. Diamond, Matthew J. Wade, and Samuel V. Scarpino, on behalf of the Global Wastewater Action Group. **"Wastewater monitoring can anchor global disease surveillance systems."** *The Lancet Global Health* 11, no. 6 (2023): e976–e981. Global. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(23\)00170-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(23)00170-5)
- Kostandova, Natalya, Catherine Schluth, Rohan Arambepola, Fatumah Atuhaire, Sophie Bérubé, Taylor Chin, Eimear Cleary, et al. **"A Systematic Review of Using Population-Level Human Mobility Data to Understand SARS-CoV-2 Transmission."** *Nature Communications* 15, no. 10504 (2024). United States, United Kingdom, France, China. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54895-7>
- Manore, Carrie, Geoffrey Fairchild, Amanda Ziemann, Nidhi Parikh, Katherine Kempfert, Kaitlyn Martinez, Lauren Castro, David Osthus, Amir Siraj, Jessica Conrad, Nicholas Generous, and Sara Del Valle. **"Unlocking the Predictive Power of Heterogeneous Data to Build an Operational Dengue Forecasting System."** *bioRxiv preprint* (2020). United States, Brazil. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.07.08.194019>
- Melo, Carolina Lopes, Larissa Rangel Mageste, Lusiele Guaraldo, Daniela Polessa Paula, and Mayumi Duarte Wakimoto. **"Use of Digital Tools in Arbovirus Surveillance: Scoping Review."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024). Brazil. <https://doi.org/10.2196/57476>
- Müller, Martin M., and Marcel Salathé. **"Crowdbreaks: Tracking Health Trends Using Public Social Media Data and Crowdsourcing."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 7 (2019): 81. Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2019.00081>
- Oliver, Nuria. **"Data Science for Social Good: The Valencian Example during the COVID-19 Pandemic."** *Open Internet Governance Institute, Paper Series #3* (June 2022). Spain. <https://www.esade.edu/ecpol/en/publications/data-science-for-social-good-the-valencian-example-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>

- Orchard, Francisco, Charline Clain, William Madie, Jessica S. Hayes, Maire A. Connolly, Etienne Sevin, and Alexis Sentís. **"PANDEM-Source, a tool to collect or generate surveillance indicators for pandemic management: a use case with COVID-19 data."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024). France, Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1295117>
- Phipps, Jesse, Bryant Passage, Kaan Sel, Jonathan Martinez, Milad Saadat, Teddy Koker, Natalie Damaso, et al. **"Early Adverse Physiological Event Detection Using Commercial Wearables: Challenges and Opportunities."** *NPJ Digital Medicine* 7, Article 136 (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01129-1>
- Sarwar, Atifa, and Emmanuel O. Agu. **"CovidRhythm: A Deep Learning Model for Passive Prediction of COVID-19 Using Biobehavioral Rhythms Derived from Wearable Physiological Data."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.10168v1*, January 12, 2023. United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.10168>
- Shandhi, Md Mobashir Hasan, Peter J. Cho, Ali R. Roghanizad, Karnika Singh, Will Wang, Oana M. Enache, Amanda Stern, Rami Sbahi, Bilge Tatar, Sean Fiscus, Qi Xuan Khoo, Yvonne Kuo, Xiao Lu, Joseph Hsieh, Alena Kalodzitsa, Amir Bahmani, Arash Alavi, Utsab Ray, Michael P. Snyder, Geoffrey S. Ginsburg, Dana K. Pasquale, Christopher W. Woods, Ryan J. Shaw, and Jessilyn P. Dunn. **"A Method for Intelligent Allocation of Diagnostic Testing by Leveraging Data from Commercial Wearable Devices: A Case Study on COVID-19."** *npj Digital Medicine* 5, no. 130 (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00672-z>
- Shi, Boyang, Weixiang Huang, Yuanyuan Dang, and Wenhui Zhou. **"Leveraging social media data for pandemic detection and prediction."** *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 11 (2024): 1075. China. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03589-y>
- St-Onge, Guillaume, Jessica T. Davis, Laurent Hébert-Dufresne, Antoine Allard, Alessandra Urbinati, Samuel V. Scarpino, Matteo Chinazzi, and Alessandro Vespignani. **"Pandemic Monitoring with Global Aircraft-Based Wastewater Surveillance Networks."** *Nature Medicine* 31, no. 3 (2025): 788–796. United States, Canada, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-025-03501-4>

- Wang, Danqi, Manuel Lentzen, Jonas Botz, Diego Valderrama, Lucille Deplante, Jules Perrio, Marie Génin, Edward Thommes, Laurent Coudeville, and Holger Fröhlich. **"Development of an Early Alert Model for Pandemic Situations in Germany."** *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 20780 (2023). Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-48096-3>
- Xie, Jiacheng, Ziyang Zhang, Shuai Zeng, Joel Hilliard, Guanghui An, Xiaoting Tang, Lei Jiang, Yang Yu, Xiufeng Wan, and Dong Xu. **"Leveraging Large Language Models for Infectious Disease Surveillance—Using a Web Service for Monitoring COVID-19 Patterns From Self-Reporting Tweets: Content Analysis."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e63190. United States, China. <https://doi.org/10.2196/63190>

B. Pandemic Preparedness and Behavioral Modeling

Typical Data Types

- Platform-Based Aggregated Mobility Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data

Use Cases

- Bolt, Kaylin, Diana Gil-González, and Nuria Oliver. **"Unconventional Data, Unprecedented Insights: Leveraging Non-Traditional Data During a Pandemic."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024): 1350743. Spain, Italy, United States. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1350743>
- Borowitz, Mariel, Janet Zhou, Krystal Azelton, and Isabelle-Yara Nassar. **"Examining the value of satellite data in halting transmission of polio in Nigeria: A socioeconomic analysis."** *Data & Policy* 5 (2023): e16. Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2023.12>

- Dhiman, Aarzo, Elad Yom-Tov, Lorenzo Pellis, Michael Edelstein, Richard Pebody, Andrew Hayward, Thomas House, Thomas Finnie, David Guzman, Vasileios Lampos, Virus Watch Consortium, and Ingemar J. Cox. **"Estimating the Household Secondary Attack Rate and Serial Interval of COVID-19 Using Social Media."** *NPJ Digital Medicine* 7, no. 194 (2024). United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01160-2>
- Glaeser, Edward L., Caitlin Gorback, and Stephen J. Redding. **"JUE Insight: How Much Does COVID-19 Increase with Mobility? Evidence from New York and Four Other U.S. Cities."** *Journal of Urban Economics* 127 (2022): 103292. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2020.103292>
- Goulding, James, Elizabeth Dolan, Gavin Long, Anya Skatova, John Harvey, Gavin Smith, and Laila Tata. **"Forecasting local COVID-19/Respiratory Disease mortality via national longitudinal shopping data: the case for integrating digital footprint data into early warning systems."** *International Journal of Population Data Science* 8, no. 3 (2023). England. <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v8i3.2290>
- Gueguen, Chloe, Nicolas Snel, and Eric Mutonji. **"Turning mobile big data insights into public health responses in times of pandemics: Lessons learnt from the Democratic Republic of the Congo."** *Data & Policy* 4 (2022): e8. Democratic Republic of the Congo. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2021.30>

2. Understanding Determinants of Health

2.1 Environmental, Structural, and Contextual Determinants of Health: How social data maps external factors affecting health

2.1.1 Built Environment and Urban Health

A. Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety

Typical Data Types

- Street-Level Imagery Data
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- GPS Trajectory Data
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Bluetooth Signal Data

Use Cases

- Bhowmick, Debapratim, Di Dai, Morteza Saberi, Timothy Nelson, Mark Stevenson, Suranga Seneviratne, Kurt Nice, Christopher Pettit, Huy Long Vu, and Brian Beck. "**Collecting population-representative bike-riding GPS data to understand bike-riding activity and patterns using smartphones and Bluetooth beacons.**" *Travel Behaviour and Society* 38 (2025): 100919. Australia. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2024.100919>
- Hamim, Omar Faruqe, and Satish V. Ukkusuri. "**Towards safer streets: A framework for unveiling pedestrians' perceived road safety using street view imagery.**" *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 195 (2024): 107400. Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.107400>.

B. Place-Based and Structural Factors

Typical Data Types

- Geospatial Datasets
- Street-Level Imagery Data
- Platform-Based Aggregated Mobility Data
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Smartphone-Native Sensing

Use Cases

- Abbasov, Timur, Cate Heine, Sadegh Sabouri, Arianna Salazar-Miranda, Paolo Santi, Edward Glaeser, and Carlo Ratti. "**Mobility Data Reveals the Trade-off Between Sustainability and Social Segregation in the 15-Minute City.**" *MIT Senseable City Lab and Harvard University*, February 2023. United States. https://iris.cnr.it/retrieve/c7506b05-4a98-4025-a6ea-60b5c04dc646/20230706_manuscript.pdf
- Boyes, Randy, William Pickett, Ian Janssen, David Swanlund, Nadine Schuurman, Louise Masse, Christina Han, and Mariana Brussoni. "**Physical Environment Features That Predict Outdoor Active Play Can Be Measured Using Google Street View Images.**" *International Journal of Health Geographics* 22 (2023): Article 26. Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12942-023-00346-3>
- Dahu, Butros M., Solaiman Khan, Imad Eddine Toubal, Mariam Alshehri, Carlos I. Martinez-Villar, Olabode B. Ogundele, Lincoln R. Sheets, and Grant J. Scott. "**Geospatial Modeling of Deep Neural Visual Features for Predicting Obesity Prevalence in Missouri: Quantitative Study.**" *JMIR AI* 3 (2024): e64362. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/64362>

- Edler, Johanna-Sophie, Michael Winter, Holger Steinmetz, Caroline Cohrdes, Harald Baumeister, and Rüdiger Pryss. **"Predicting Depressive Symptoms Using GPS-Based Regional Data in Germany With the CORONA HEALTH App During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Cross-Sectional Study."** *Interactive Journal of Medical Research* 13 (2024): e53248. Germany. <https://doi.org/10.2196/53248>
- Glaeser, Edward L., Michael Greenstone, Stephen P. Ryan, Ishan Nath, and Daniel Sullivan. **"Infrastructure Inequality: Who Pays the Cost of Road Roughness?"** *National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper No. 31939*, December 2023. United States. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31939>.
- Poorthuis, Ate, Qianhui Chen, and Matthew Zook. **"A nationwide dataset of de-identified activity spaces derived from geotagged social media data."** *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science* 0(0) (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083241264051>
- Sinclair, Michael, Rania Sermpezi, Qunshan Zhao, Richard Mitchell, and Nick Bailey. **"Estimating greenspace visitation using Digital Footprints Data: A collaboration with Glasgow City Council to aid in Open Space policy and operations."** *GIScience 2023 Conference Poster* (2023). United Kingdom. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/3xzsv_v1
- Srinivasan, Karthik, Faiz Currim, Casey M. Lindberg, Javad Razjouyan, Brian Gilligan, Hyoki Lee, Kelli J. Canada, Nicole Goebel, Matthias R. Mehl, Melissa M. Lunden, Judith Heerwagen, Bijan Najafi, Esther M. Sternberg, Kevin Kampschroer, and Sudha Ram. **"Discovery of associative patterns between workplace sound level and physiological wellbeing using wearable devices and empirical Bayes modeling."** *npj Digital Medicine* 6, no. 5 (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00727-1>
- Tai, Xiao Hui, Shikhar Mehra, and Joshua E. Blumenstock. **"Mobile phone data reveal the effects of violence on internal displacement in Afghanistan."** *Nature Human Behaviour* 6 (2022): 624–634. Afghanistan. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01336-4>

2.1.2 Natural Environment and Climate Exposure

A. Air Quality, Pollution, and Health

Typical Data Types

- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data
- Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data
- Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Use Cases

- Gu, Dongxiao, Qin Wang, Yidong Chai, Xuejie Yang, Wang Zhao, Min Li, Oleg Zolotarev, Zhengfei Xu & Gongrang Zhang. "**Identifying the Risk Factors of Allergic Rhinitis Based on Zhihu Comment Data Using a Topic-Enhanced Word-Embedding Model: Mixed Method Study and Cluster Analysis.**" *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024). China, Russia. <https://doi.org/10.2196/48324>.
- Pennington, Audrey F., Ambarish Vaidyanathan, Farah S. Ahmed, Arie Manangan, Maria C. Mirabelli, Kanta Devi Sircar, Fuyuen Yip, and W. Dana Flanders. "**Large-Scale Agricultural Burning and Cardiorespiratory Emergency Department Visits in the U.S. State of Kansas.**" *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology* 33, no. 4 (2023): 663–669. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-023-00531-3>
- Pérez-Pérez, Martín, María Fernandez Gonzalez, Francisco Javier Rodriguez-Rajo, and Florentino Fdez-Riverola. "**Tracking the Spread of Pollen on Social Media Using Pollen-Related Messages From Twitter: Retrospective Analysis.**" *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e58309. Spain. <https://doi.org/10.2196/58309>
- Wu, Lili, Chenyin Gao, Shu Yang, Brian J. Reich, and Ana G. Rappold. "**Estimating Spatially Varying Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke Using Mobile Health Data.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.12017v3* (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.12017>

2.1.3 Disaster Risk and Resilience

A. Disaster Response and Recovery

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Mapping Platform and Crowdsourced Mapping Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals
- Smart City Camera and Sensor Data
- News Media and News Content Data

Use Cases

- Firmansyah, Hafiz Budi, Jose Luis Fernandez-Marquez, Mehmet Oguz Mulayim, Jorge Gomes, and Valerio Lorini. "**Accelerating Crisis Response: Automated Image Classification for Geolocating Social Media Content.**" 2023 *IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM)* (2023). Switzerland, Spain, Portugal, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3625007.3627831>.
- Gündoğmuş, Eray. "**How an Open-Source Disaster Map Helped Thousands of Earthquake Survivors: afetharita.com.**" *DEV Community* (2023). Turkey. <https://dev.to/erayg/how-an-open-source-disaster-map-helped-thousands-of-earthquake-survivors-afetharita.com-440>
- Liberal Democratic Party Policy Research Council of Japan. Proposals on Promoting Disaster Prevention DX: "**Digital That Connects Lives - New Era of Disaster Prevention**". 2023. Japan. https://www.cas.go.jp/jp/seisaku/bousai_dx/dai1/siryou2.pdf.
- Mitsubishi Estate Co., Ltd. Area Disaster Preparedness Efforts in Otemachi, Marunouchi, and Yurakucho: Demonstration of the "**Disaster Dashboard Beta+ Platform for Information Coordination During Disasters (2023)**." Japan. https://www.mec.co.jp/news/detail/2023/02/08_mec230208_saigaidashboardbetaplus
- Moghadas, Mojtaba, Alexander Fekete, Abbas Rajabifard, and Theo Koetter. "**The wisdom of crowds for improved disaster resilience: a near-real-time analysis of crowdsourced social media data on the 2021 flood in Germany.**" *GeoJournal* 88 (2023): 4215–4241. Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-023-10858-x>

B. Early Warning via Social Sensing

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Crowdsourced Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Traffic and Transport Flow Data
- Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

Use Cases

- Cicek, Didem, and Burak Kantarci. "**Use of mobile crowdsensing in disaster management: A systematic review, challenges, and open issues.**" *Sensors* 23, no. 3 (2023). Canada. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031699>
- Senarath, Yasas, Ayan Mukhopadhyay, Hemant Purohit, and Abhishek Dubey. "**Designing a human-centered AI tool for proactive incident detection using crowdsourced data sources to support emergency response.**" *Digital Government: Research and Practice* 5, no. 1 (2024): Article 9. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3633784>

C. Evacuation Patterns and Shelter Coordination

Typical Data Types

- Telecom mobility data (CDRs)
- Platform-based aggregated mobility data
- Geospatial datasets
- Mapping platform data

Use Cases

- Naushirvanov, T., E. Elejalde, K. Kalimeri, E. Omodei, M. Karsai, and L. Ferres. "**Evacuation patterns and socioeconomic stratification in the context of wildfires in Chile.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.06017* (2024). Chile. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.06017>

2.2 Behavioral and Social Determinants of Health: How social data maps behavioral and social determinants

2.2.1 Consumption Patterns and Health Outcomes

A. Nutrition, Food Security, and Consumption Surveillance

Typical Data Types

- Shopping Data
- Retail Product Review and Retail Data
- Aggregated Consumer and Marketing Data
- Geospatial datasets

Use Cases

- Burgess, Romana, Alisha Suhag, and Anya Skatova. **"Loyalty Card Data for Assessing Dietary Interventions: A Narrative Review."** *Preprint, University of Bristol*, 2025. United Kingdom. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/9dg48_v1
- Fan, Jungwei W., Wanjing Wang, Ming Huang, Hongfang Liu, and W. Michael Hooten. **"Retrospective content analysis of consumer product reviews related to chronic pain."** *Frontiers in Digital Health* 5 (2023): 958338. United States. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdqth.2023.958338>

- Iqbal, M., M.A. Morris, and J.E. Cade. **"Understanding Searches for 'Weight Loss' Using Google Trends."** *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society* 83, OCE4 (2024): E387. United Kingdom, Indonesia. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0029665124006256>
- Mansilla, Roberto, Gavin Long, Simon Welham, John Harvey, Evgeniya Lukinova, Georgiana Nica-Avram, Gavin Smith, David Salt, Andrew Smith, and James Goulding. **"Detecting iodine deficiency risks from dietary transitions using shopping data."** *Scientific Reports* 14 (2024): 1017. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50180-7>
- Morris, Michelle, Victoria Jenneson, and Georgia D Tomova. **"Is eye-level health messaging effective in encouraging 'healthier' snack choices, in the context of 'meal deal' offers?"** *OSF Preprint* (2024). United Kingdom. <https://osf.io/2fc7n/resources>
- Ravandi, Babak, Gordana Ispirova, Michael Sebek, Peter Mehler, Albert-László Barabási, and Giulia Menichetti. **"Prevalence of Processed Foods in Major US Grocery Stores."** *Nature Food* 6 (2025): 296–308. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-024-01095-7>

- Skatova, Anya. **"Overcoming Biases of Individual-Level Shopping History Data in Health Research."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7 (2024): 264. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01231-4>
- Suhag, Alisha, Romana Burgess, and Anya Skatova. **"Shopping Data for Epidemiological Research: Opportunities, Challenges, and Future Directions."** *Preprint, University of Bristol*, 2023. United Kingdom. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/8ez4j_v1
- Thomas, Madeleine, J. Bernadette Moore, Diogo Ann Onuselogu, Alexandra Dalton, Tim Rains, Emer Lowry, Nilani Sritharan, and Michelle A. Morris. **"Supermarket top-up of Healthy Start vouchers increases fruit and vegetable purchases in low-income households."** *Nutrition Bulletin* 48 (2023): 353–364. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nbu.12627>

B. Advertising, Marketing, and Behavioral Health Risks

Typical Data Types

- Aggregated Consumer and Marketing Data
- Shopping Data

Use Cases

- Arrona-Cardoza, Pablo, Katherine Labonté, José Miguel Cisneros-Franco, and Daiva E. Nielsen. **"The effects of food advertisements on food intake and neural activity: A systematic review and meta-analysis of recent experimental studies."** *Advances in Nutrition* 14 (2023): 339–351. Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advnut.2022.12.003>

C. Spatial and Socioeconomic Disparities in Access

Typical Data Types

- Shopping Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Mobility and Geolocation Data

Use Cases

- Althoff, Tim, Hamed Nilforoshan, Jenna Hua, and Jure Leskovec. **"Large-Scale Diet Tracking Data Reveal Disparate Associations Between Food Environment and Diet."** *Nature Communications* 13, no. 267 (2022). United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27522-y>
- Cook, Cody, Lindsey Currier, and Edward Glaeser. **"Urban Mobility and the Experienced Isolation of Students."** *Nature Cities* 1 (2024): 73–82. United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44284-023-00007-3>
- Fearne, Andrew, Natalia Borzino, Beatrix De La Iglesia, Peter Moffatt, and Margaret Robbins. **"Using Supermarket Loyalty Card Data to Measure the Differential Impact of the UK Soft Drink Sugar Tax on Buyer Behaviour."** *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 73 (2022): 321–337. United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12462>
- Harvey, John, Gavin Long, Roberto Mansilla, Simon Welham, Peter Rose, Michelle Thomas, Gregor Milligan, Elizabeth Dolan, Joanne Parkes, Kuzivakwashe Makokoro, and James Goulding. **"Who consumes anthocyanins and anthocyanidins? Mining national retail data to reveal the influence of socioeconomic deprivation and seasonality on polyphenol dietary intake."** In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*, 4530–4538. England.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData59044.2023.10386220>
- Smith, Lindsey G., Maggie Yifei Ma, Michael J. Widener, and Steven Farber. **"Geographies of Grocery Shopping in Major Canadian Cities: Evidence from Large-Scale Mobile App Data."** *PsyArXiv Preprints* (2022). Canada.
https://osf.io/preprints/osf/kjsdz_v1

2.2.2 Socioeconomic, Housing, and Migration Contexts of Health

A. Economic and Social Mobility Factors

Typical Data Types

- Financial Transaction Data
- Geospatial Datasets
- Social Media Networks and Architectures

Use Cases

- Balla-Elliott, Dylan, Zoë B. Cullen, Edward L. Glaeser, Michael Luca, and Christopher T. Stanton. **"Determinants of Small Business Reopening Decisions After COVID Restrictions Were Lifted."** NBER Working Paper 27362, revised September 2021. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research. United States. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w27362>
- Chetty, Raj, John N. Friedman, Michael Stepner, and the Opportunity Insights Team. **"The Economic Impacts of COVID-19: Evidence from a New Public Database Built Using Private Sector Data."** April 2023. United States. <https://opportunityinsights.org/paper/tracker/>

- Harris, Tom, Shankar Iyer, Tom Rutter, Guanghua Chi, Drew Johnston, Patrick Lam, Lucy Makinson, Antonio S. Silva, Martin Wessel, Mei-Chen (Zoe) Liou, Yingcan Wang, Qamar Zaman, and Michael Bailey. **"Social Capital in the United Kingdom: Evidence from Six Billion Friendships."** *OSF Preprints*, March 21, 2025. United Kingdom. https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/kb7dy_v1
- Kazmina, Yuliia, Eelke M. Heemskerk, Emilia van der Kooij, Eszter Bokányi, and Frank W. Takes. **"Can Social Capital Remedy Structural Inequality? Economic Mobility in a Longitudinal Population-Scale Social Network."** *arXiv Preprint*, August 7, 2025. Netherlands. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.05275>.

B. Housing and Homelessness Dynamics

Typical Data Types

- Street-Level Imagery Data
- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals

Use Cases

- Bird, Yoshi M., Sarah E. Grobe, Michael V. Arnold, Sean P. Rogers, Mikaela I. Fudolig, Julia Witte Zimmerman, Christopher M. Danforth, and Peter Sheridan Dodds. "An Assessment of Measuring Local Levels of Homelessness Through Proxy Social Media Signals." *International Journal on Homelessness* 5, no. 2 (2025): 4–34. United States. <https://doi.org/10.5206/ijoh.2023.3.16467>
- Blumenstock, Joshua E., Guanghua Chi, and Xu Tan. "Migration and the Value of Social Networks." *The Review of Economic Studies* 92, no. 1 (January 2025): 97–128. Rwanda. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdad113>.
- Jung, Wooyong, Sola Kim, Dongwook Kim, Maryam Tabar, and Dongwon Lee. "A New Lens on Homelessness: Daily Tent Monitoring with 311 Calls and Street Images." arXiv Preprint, 2024. United States. <https://arxiv.org/html/2508.06409v1>
- Marler, Will. "'You Can Connect with Like, the World!': Social Platforms, Survival Support, and Digital Inequalities for People Experiencing Homelessness." *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 27, no. 1 (January 2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcmc/zmab020>

- Ranjit, Jaspreet, Brihi Joshi, Rebecca Dorn, Laura Petry, Olga Koumoundouros, Jayne Bottarini, Peichen Liu, Eric Rice, and Swabha Swayamdipta. "OATH-Frames: Characterizing Online Attitudes Towards Homelessness with LLM Assistants." arXiv preprints, October 28, 2024. United States. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.14883>

C. Migration and Transnational Networks

Typical Data Types

- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals

Use Cases

- Dzansi, Gladys, Amankwa Abdul-Mumim, William Menkah, Vivian Ametefe, Eugenia Xatse, and Believe Adzoa Azanku. "Influence of Social Media and the Digital Environment on International Migration of Health Workforce from Low- and Middle-Income Countries Post COVID-19 Pandemic: A Scoping Review Protocol." *BMJ Open* 14, no. 10 (2024): e087213. Multiple LMICs. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2024-087213>

- Kim, Jisu, Soazic Elise Wang Sonne, Kiran Garimella, André Grow, Ingmar Weber, and Emilio Zagheni. "**Online Social Integration of Migrants: Evidence from Twitter.**" *Migration Studies* 11, no. 4 (December 2023): 544–571. Multiple countries. <https://doi.org/10.1093/migration/mnad017>
- Minora, Umberto, Martina Belmonte, Claudio Bosco, Drew Johnston, Eugenia Giraudy, Stefano M. Iacus, and Francesco Sermi. "**Migration Patterns, Friendship Networks, and the Diaspora: The Potential of Facebook's Social Connectedness Index to Anticipate Displacement Patterns Induced by Russia's Invasion of Ukraine in the European Union.**" arXiv, December 15, 2022. European Union. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.01833>
- Sahai, Harshil, and Mike Bailey. "**Social Networks and Spatial Mobility: Evidence from Facebook in India.**" arXiv, March 2022. India. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.05595>

3. Examining Structural Drivers

3.1 Structural Drivers of Population Differences and Inequities: How social data enables a population and equity lens across all domains

3.1.1 Structural Drivers of Population Differences and Inequities

A. Research from and about health equity in LMICs (Low- and Middle-Income Countries)*

**Several other examples of research led by LMICs can be found throughout the Reference Guide*

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
AI-Generated Health Insights
- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data
- Geospatial Datasets

Use Cases

- Koebe, Till, Theophilus Aidoo, Ridhi Kashyap, Douglas R. Leasure, Valentina Rotondi, and Ingmar Weber. "**Social capital mediates knowledge gaps in informing sexual and reproductive health behaviours across Africa.**" *Social Science & Medicine* 357 (2024): 117159. Germany, United Kingdom.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277953624006129?via%3Dihub>
- Mafuya, Phaswana, Refilwe Nancy, Edith Phalane, Amrita Rao, Kalai Willis, Katherine Rucinski, K. Alida Voet, Amal Abdulrahman, Claris Siyamayambo, Betty Sebati, Mohlago Seloka, Musa Jaiteh, Lerato Lucia Olifant, Katharine Journeay, Haley Sisel, Xiaoming Li, Bankole Olatosi, Neset Hikmet, Prashant Duhoon, Francois Wolmarans, Yegnanew A. Shiferaw, Lifutso Motsieloa, Mashudu Rampilo, and Stefan Baral. "**Harnessing Big Heterogeneous Data to Evaluate the Potential Impact of HIV Responses Among Key Populations in Sub-Saharan Africa: Protocol for the Boloka Data Repository Initiative.**" *JMIR Research Protocols* 14 (2025): e63583. South Africa.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/63583>
- Mueller, Sonja, Katerina Stavrianaki, Andrei Boscor, Naomi Saville, Abriti Arjyal, Sushil Baral, Maureen Fordham, Gareth Hearn, and Patty Kostkova. "**MANTRA game analytics: Effectiveness of educational mobile game on knowledge gain and retention of Female Community Health Volunteers (FCHVs) and women in rural Nepal assessed through game analytics.**" Preprint, Research Square (2024). Nepal.
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3850669/v1>
- Taylor, Elisa, Manu Airaksinen, Rikhard Ihamuotila, Milja Kivelä, Ulla Ashorn, Leena M. Haataja, Charles Mangani & Sampsa Vanhatalo. "**Assessing motor development with wearables in low-resource settings: feasibility in rural Malawi.**" *Pediatric Research* (2025). Malawi, Finland.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-025-03818-3>.
- Zhang, Miao, Hajra Arshad, Manzar Abbas, Hamzah Jehanzeb, Izza Tahir, Javerya Hassan, Zainab Samad, and Rumi Chunara. "**Quantifying Greenspace with Satellite Images in Karachi, Pakistan, Using a New Data Augmentation Paradigm.**" *ACM Journal on Computing and Sustainable Societies* 3, no. 1 (March 2025): Article 6, 1–23. Pakistan. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3716370>

B. Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities

Typical Data Types

- Telecom Mobility Data (CDRs)
- Platform-Based Aggregated Mobility Data
- Smartphone Location Tracking
- Transportation Mode Detection
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Derecki, Raphael, Brian O'Shea, and James Goulding. "**Leveraging Multiple Digital Footprint Datasets to Predict Racial, Sex-Based, and Sexual-Orientation Bias Across US States.**" *International Journal of Population Data Science* 9, no. 4 (2024): 15. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v9i4.2429>
- Duncan, Dustin T., Stephanie H. Cook, Erica P. Wood, Seann D. Regan, Basile Chaix, Yijun Tian, and Rumi Chunara. "**Structural racism and homophobia evaluated through social media sentiment combined with activity spaces and associations with mental health among young sexual minority men.**" *Social Science & Medicine* 338 (2023): 115755. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.115755>.
- Hwang, Sungjin, Jiwoong Heo, Youngwug Cho, Jucheol Moon, Yushin Lee, Hansung Kim, Jaehyuk Cha, and Kwanguk Kim. "**Transportation Mode Detection Technology to Predict Wheelchair Users' Life Satisfaction in Seoul, South Korea.**" *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 8, no. 1 (2024): Article 9. South Korea, United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3643506>
- Naushirvanov, T., E. Elejalde, K. Kalimeri, E. Omodei, M. Karsai, and L. Ferres. "**Evacuation patterns and socioeconomic stratification in the context of wildfires in Chile.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.06017* (2024). Chile. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.06017>
- Park, Hyun Joon, Sara Chari Francisco, M. Rosemary Pang, Lulu Peng, and Guangqing Chi. "**Exposure to anti-Black Lives Matter movement and obesity of the Black population.**" *Social Science & Medicine* 316 (2023): 114265. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114265>.
- Riccio, Piera, Julien Colin, Shirley Ogolla, and Nuria Oliver. "**Mirror, Mirror on the Wall, Who Is the Whitest of All? Racial Biases in Social Media Beauty Filters.**" *Social Media + Society* (2024): 1–15. Spain, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051241239295>

- Shrivastava, Shreya, Tarika Jain, Kim D'Souza, Shreyashi Ray, Nihal Sahu, and Rituparna Padhy. **"Holding Healthcare Providers Accountable: Consumer, Civil, and Criminal Mechanisms."** *Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy*, December 5, 2023. India. <https://vidhilegalpolicy.in/research/holding-healthcare-providers-accountable-consumer-civil-and-criminal-mechanisms>

C. Age-Specific Applications (Children, Elderly)

Typical Data Types

- Smart City Camera and Sensor Data
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Wearable-Derived Contextual and Environmental Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Baghezza, Rani, Kévin Bouchard, and Charles Gouin-Vallerand. **"Recognizing the Age, Gender, and Mobility of Pedestrians in Smart Cities using a CNN-BGRU on Thermal Images."** *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Information Technology for Social Good (GoodIT '22)*, 48–54 (2022). Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3524458.3547235>.

- Kadirvelu, Balasundaram, Teresa Bellido Bel, Aglaia Freccero, Martina Di Simplicio, Dasha Nicholls, A. Aldo Faisal. **"Digital Phenotyping for Adolescent Mental Health: A Feasibility Study Employing Machine Learning to Predict Mental Health Risk From Active and Passive Smartphone Data."** *Preprint* (2024). United Kingdom, Germany. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.08851>
- Liu, Muhan, Yang Shi, Wenyu Liu, and Huamin Qu. **"HealthPrism: A Visual Analytics System for Exploring Children's Physical and Mental Health Profiles."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.12242v2*, (2023). Hong Kong. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.12242>
- Shoda, Vera Paola. **"From status updates to states of mind: analyzing parental well-being in the digital landscape."** *PsyArXiv Preprint, Kobe University* (2023). Japan. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/pcxfe_v1
- Singh, Karnika, Sarah C. Armstrong, Brooke E. Wagner, Julie Counts, Asheley Skinner, Melissa Kay, Jennifer S. Li, Svati Shah, Nancy Zucker, Cody Neshteruk, Mary Story, Lilianna Suarez, William E. Kraus, Alexandra R. Zizzi, and Jessilyn Dunn. **"Physical activity and sleep changes among children during the COVID-19 pandemic."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7 (2024): 70. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01041-8>

- Ward, Jamie A., Yanke Sun, Maria Bell, Thomas Gilbert, Sally Day, and Antonia F. de C. Hamilton. **"Wearable sensors can track social interaction in groups of autistic and non-autistic children."** *PsyArXiv Preprint*. United Kingdom. <https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/smzfx.v1>.

D. Gender and Health Inequities

Typical Data Types

- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Use Cases

- Foriest, Jasmine C., Shravika Mittal, Kirsten Bray, Anh-Ton Tran, and Munmun De Choudhury. **"A Cross Community Comparison of Muting in Conversations of Gendered Violence on Reddit."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 8, CSCW2, Article 401 (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3686940>
- Rodrick, Stanley Sumon, Hamidul Islam, Sahin Akter Sarker, and Mousomi Hridoy Hema. **"Branding and Promotional Incentives on Purchase Behavior for Sanitary Napkins among Young Adult Female Consumers in Bangladesh."** *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews* 7, no. 4 (2024): 356–373. Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1992.07.04.644>

- Sivill, Terty, Vanja Ljevar, James Goulding, and Anya Skatova. **"What can transactional data reveal about the prevalence of menstrual pain in England?"** *International Journal of Population Data Science* 8, no. 3 (2023). England. <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v8i3.2272>
- Vennells, Louise. **"Global researchers team with menstrual health app Clue to research female health conditions."** *University of Exeter News*, December 14, 2023. Germany, United Kingdom. <https://news.exeter.ac.uk/faculty-of-health-and-life-sciences/global-researchers-team-with-menstrual-health-app-clue-to-research-female-health-conditions/>

3.2 Health Communication and Social Dynamics:

How social data informs public discourse, knowledge diffusion, and health-related decision-making

3.2.1 Mental Health Expression and Peer Support Online

A. Expressions of Distress, Help-Seeking Behavior, Community Support

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Social Media Metadata
- Online Discussion Forums
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- Social Media Networks and Architectures

Use Cases

- Bickham, Charles, Kia Kazemi-Nia, Luca Luceri, Kristina Lerman, and Emilio Ferrara. **"Hidden in Plain Sight: Exploring the Intersections of Mental Health, Eating Disorders, and Content Moderation on TikTok."** *Proceedings of the ICWSM Workshops*. (2024). United States. https://workshop-proceedings.icwsm.org/abstract.php?id=2024_23
- Bouzoubaa, Layla, and Rezvaneh Rezapour. **"Euphoria's Hidden Voices: Examining Emotional Resonance and Shared Substance Use Experience of Viewers on Reddit."** *Proceedings of the ICWSM Workshops* (2024). United States. https://workshop-proceedings.icwsm.org/abstract.php?id=2024_22
- Frederiksen, Kristian Steen, Julie Hahn-Pedersen, Rebecca Crawford, Ross Morrison, Rose Jeppesen, Lynda Doward, and Wendy Weidner. **"Traversing Shifting Sands—the Challenges of Caring for Someone With Alzheimer's Disease and the Impact on Care Partners: Social Media Content Analysis."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e55468. Denmark, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.2196/55468>

- García, Yury E., Miryam Elizabeth Villa-Pérez, Kuang Li, Xiao Hui Tai, Luis A. Trejo, Maria L. Daza-Torres, J. Cricelio Montesinos-López, and Miriam Nuño. **"Wildfires and Social Media Discourse: Exploring Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing Through Twitter."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024): 1349609. United States, Mexico. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1349609>
- Hswen, Yulin, Qiuyuan Qin, Pressley Smith, Alison Swierczynski, Stuart Bauer, Erika Ladson, Amanda Leigh Garrett, and Catherine A. Brownstein. **"Sentiments of Individuals with Interstitial Cystitis/Bladder Pain Syndrome Toward Pentosan Polysulfate Sodium: Infodemiology Study."** *JMIR Formative Research* 9 (2025): e54209. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/54209>
- Lindgren, Simon, and Lorna Richardson. **"Endometriosis Pain and Epistemic Community: Mapping Discourses in Online Discussions Among Sufferers."** *Social Science & Medicine* 326 (2023): 115889. Sweden, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.115889>
- Nicmanis, Mitchell, Joshua Holmes, Melissa Oxlad, and Anna Chur-Hansen. **"Patient Information Needs and Decision-Making Before a Cardiac Implantable Electronic Device: A Qualitative Study Utilizing Social Media Data."** *Journal of Clinical Psychology in Medical Settings* 32 (2025): 121–130. Australia. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10880-024-10024-6>
- Pleasants, Elizabeth, Lindsay Parham, Karen Weidert, Emma Anderson, Eliza Dolgins, Ndola Prata, Ushma D. Upadhyay, and Cassandra Marshall. **"Waiting to start abortion: A qualitative exploration of narratives of waiting shared in a Reddit community for abortion post-Dobbs leak in 2022."** *Social Science & Medicine* 349 (2024): 116877. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2024.116877>
- Rani, Saima, Khandakar Ahmed, and Sudha Subramani. **"From Posts to Knowledge: Annotating a Pandemic-Era Reddit Dataset to Navigate Mental Health Narratives."** *Applied Sciences* 14(4) (2024): 1547. Australia. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14041547>

3.2.2 Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy

A. Chronic Illness Perceptions

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Online Discussion Forums
- Blogs and Microblogs
- Social Media Metadata
- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- AI-Generated Health Insights

Use Cases

- Hwang, Hee Jeong, Nara Kim, Jeong Yun You, Hye Ri Ryu, Seo-Young Kim, Jung Han Yoon Park, and Ki Won Lee. **"Harnessing Social Media Data to Understand Information Needs About Kidney Diseases and Emotional Experiences With Disease Management: Topic and Sentiment Analysis."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e64838. South Korea.
<https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e64838>
- King, Andy J., Natalie M. Dunbar, Drew Margolin, Rumi Chunara, Chau Tong, Lea Jih-Vieira, Cindy B. Matsen, and Jeff Niederdeppe. **"Global Prevalence and Content of Information about Alcohol Use as a Cancer Risk Factor on Twitter."** *Preventive Medicine* 177 (2023): 107728. United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2023.107728>
- Ljevar, Vanja, Alexa Spence, and James Goulding. **"Small talk, Big data: Patients' and general public's perceptions about patients."** *PsyArXiv Preprint*. (2022). United Kingdom.
https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/f4z57_v1
- Micale, Cristina, Su Golder, Karen O'Connor, Davy Weissenbacher, Robert Gross, Sean Hennessy, and Graciela Gonzalez-Hernandez. **"Patient-Reported Reasons for Antihypertensive Medication Change: A Quantitative Study Using Social Media."** *Drug Safety* 47 (2024): 81–91. United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40264-023-01366-5>
- Orr, Natalie, Rebecca Abbott, and Rebecca Barnes. **"Reviewing the Evidence Base for Topical Steroid Withdrawal Syndrome in the Research Literature and Social Media Platforms: An Evidence Gap Map."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e57687. United Kingdom.
<https://www.jmir.org/2024/1/e57687>
- Parveen, Sana, Agustin Garcia Pereira, Nathaly Garzon-Orjuela, Patricia McHugh, Aswathi Surendran, Heike Vornhagen, and Akke Vellinga. **"COVID-19 Public Health Communication on X (Formerly Twitter): Cross-Sectional Study of Message Type, Sentiment, and Source."** *JMIR Formative Research* 9 (2025): e59687. Ireland, United Kingdom.
<https://formative.jmir.org/2025/1/e59687>
- Peerawong, Thanarpan, Tharin Phenwan, Meiko Makita, Sojirat Supanichwatana, Panupong Puttarak, Naowanit Siammai, and Prakaidao Sunthorn. **"Evaluating Online Cannabis Health Information for Thai Breast Cancer Survivors Using the Quality Evaluation Scoring Tool (QUEST): Mixed Method Study."** *JMIR Cancer* 10 (2024): e55300. Thailand.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/55300>
- Sezgin, Serra, Canan Sümeýra Gün, Mehmet Can Uğur, and Selmin Şenol. **"Hemophilia tweets in Turkey: A rare disease and scarce policies."** *Social Science & Medicine* 373 (2025): 117937. Turkey.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2025.117937>

- Tong, Chau, Drew Margolin, Rumi Chunara, Jeff Niederdeppe, Teairah Taylor, Natalie Dunbar, and Andy J. King. **"Search Term Identification Methods for Computational Health Communication: Word Embedding and Network Approach for Health Content on YouTube."** *JMIR Medical Informatics* 10, no. 8 (2022): e37862. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/37862>
- Wu, Xingyue, Chun Sing Lam, Ka Ho Hui, Herbert Ho-fung Loong, Keary Rui Zhou, Chun-Kit Ngan, and Yin Ting Cheung. **"Perceptions in 3.6 Million Web-Based Posts of Online Communities on the Use of Cancer Immunotherapy: Data Mining Using BERTopic."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e60948. Hong Kong. <https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e60948>

B. Vaccination Sentiment and Misinformation Spread

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Online Discussion Forums
- Blogs and Microblogs
- Social Media Metadata
- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- Online Search Behavior

- Online Product Review and Retail Data
- Crowdsourced Media Content and Annotations

Use Cases

- Aldosery, Aisha, Robert Carruthers, Karandeep Kay, Christian Cave, Paul Reynolds, and Patty Kostkova. **"Enhancing public health response: a framework for topics and sentiment analysis of COVID-19 in the UK using Twitter and the embedded topic model."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024): 1105383. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1105383>
- Chau, Brian, Melody Taba, Rachael Dodd, Kirsten McCaffery, and Carissa Bonner. **"Twitch Data in Health Promotion Research: Protocol for a Case Study Exploring COVID-19 Vaccination Views Among Young People."** *JMIR Research Protocols* 12 (2023): e48641. Australia. <https://doi.org/10.2196/48641>.
- Insecurity Insight. **"Protecting the Humanitarian Space to Deliver Health Care during the Mpox Public Health Emergency."** Switzerland: *Insecurity Insight*, 2024. Burundi, Cameroon, CAR, DRC, Nigeria, Uganda. <https://bit.ly/SMMMmpoxDec2024>
- Li, Xintian, and Aron Culotta. **"Forecasting COVID-19 Vaccination Rates using Social Media Data."** *Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023 (WWW '23 Companion)* (2023). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543873.3587639>

- Lohiniva, Anna-Leena, Annika Pensola, Suvi Hyökki, Jonas Sivelä, Vuokko Härmä, and Tuukka Tammi. **"Identifying Factors Influencing COVID-19 Vaccine Uptake in Finland – A Qualitative Study Using Social Media Data."** *Frontiers in Public Health* 11 (2023): 1138800. Finland. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1138800>
- O'Brien, Gabrielle, Ronith Ganjigunta, and Paramveer S. Dhillon. **"Wellness Influencer Responses to COVID-19 Vaccines on Social Media: A Longitudinal Observational Study."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e56651. United States. <https://www.jmir.org/2024/1/e56651>
- Teng, Shasha, Nan Jiang, and Kok Wei Khong. **"Using big data to understand the online ecology of COVID-19 vaccination hesitancy."** *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 9, no. 158 (2022). Malaysia. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01185-6>
- Valdez, Danny, Arthur D. Soto-Vásquez, and María S. Montenegro. **"Geospatial Vaccine Misinformation Risk on Social Media: Online Insights From an English/Spanish Natural Language Processing (NLP) Analysis of Vaccine-Related Tweets."** *Social Science & Medicine* 339 (2023): 116365. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.116365>

C. Trust in Health Authorities

Typical Data Sources

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Social Media Networks and Architectures
- Social Media Metadata
- AI-Generated Health Insights

Use Cases

- Insecurity Insight. **"MSF Ambush in Burkina Faso: Social Media Monitoring, March 2023."** Switzerland: Insecurity Insight, 2023. Burkina Faso. <https://bit.ly/MSFBurkinaSMMMMar2023>
- Li, Yao-Tai, Man-Lin Chen, and Hsuan-Wei Lee. **"Health Communication on Social Media at the Early Stage of the Pandemic: Examining Health Professionals' COVID-19 Related Tweets."** *Social Science & Medicine* 347 (2024): 116748. Australia, Taiwan. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2024.116748>

- Wehrli, Silvan, Christopher Irrgang, Mark Scott, Bert Arnrich, and T. Sonia Boender. "**The Role of the (In)accessibility of Social Media Data for Infodemic Management: A Public Health Perspective on the Situation in the European Union in March 2024.**" *Frontiers in Public Health* 12 (2024): 1378412. Germany, United States, Netherlands.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1378412>

3.2.3 Peer Influence, Social Capital, and Behavior Change

A. Health Behavior Diffusion in Online Networks

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Social Media Networks and Architectures

Use Cases

- Ahmed, Wasim, Mariann Hardey, and Josep Vidal-Alaball. "**Organ Donation Conversations on X and Development of the OrgReach Social Media Marketing Strategy: Social Network Analysis.**" *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e59872. United Kingdom, Spain.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/59872>

- Burgess, Romana, Alisha Suhag, and Anya Skatova. "**Exploring the Use of Supermarket Loyalty Card Data in Health Research: A Scoping Review.**" Preprint, OSF, May 2025. United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/E9ZHW>
- Gulati, Aditya, Marina Martínez-García, Daniel Fernández, Miguel Angel Lozano, Bruno Lepri, and Nuria Oliver. "**What Is Beautiful Is Still Good: The Attractiveness Halo Effect in the Era of Beauty Filters.**" *Royal Society Open Science* 11 (2024): 240882. Spain, Italy.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240882>

4. Cross-Cutting Issues

4.1 Augmented Health Knowledge Systems and Decision Support: How AI and integrated data systems enhance knowledge, prediction, and action

4.1.1 AI-Augmented Health Interfaces and Knowledge Systems

A. Empathic AI for Mental Health Support

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Contextual and Environmental Data
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data
- Synthetic and Simulated Health Data

Use Cases

- Dongre, Poorvesh. "**Physiology-Driven Empathic Large Language Models (EmLLMs) for Mental Health Support.**" *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA)* Article No. 452, 1–5. (2024). United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3613905.3651132>.
- Merrill, Mike A., Akshay Paruchuri, Naghmeh Rezaei, Geza Kovacs, Javier Perez, Yun Liu, Erik Schenck, et al. "**Transforming Wearable Data into Health Insights Using Large Language Model Agents.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.06464v2* (2024). United States.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.06464>
- Yang, Kailai, Tianlin Zhang, Ziyang Kuang, Qianqian Xie, Jimin Huang, and Sophia Ananiadou. "**MentaLLaMA: Interpretable Mental Health Analysis on Social Media with Large Language Models.**" *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2024 (WWW '24)*, 2024, Article No. 3648137. China, United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3589334.3648137>

B. Personalized Coaching and Prediction Systems

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Wearable-Derived Contextual and Environmental Data
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- Synthetic and Simulated Health Data

Use Cases

- Erturk, Eray, Fahad Kamran, Salar Abbaspourazad, Sean Jewell, Harsh Sharma, Yujie Li, Sinead Williamson, Nicholas J. Foti, and Joseph Futoma. **"Beyond Sensor Data: Foundation Models of Behavioral Data from Wearables Improve Health Predictions."** arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.00191, July 2025. United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.00191>
- Feli, Mohammad, Iman Azimi, Pasi Liljeberg, and Amir M. Rahmani. **"An LLM-Powered Agent for Physiological Data Analysis: A Case Study on PPG-based Heart Rate Estimation."** arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.12836v2 (2025). Finland, United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.12836>
- Jörke, Matthew, Shardul Sapkota, Lyndsea Warkenthien, Niklas Vainio, Paul Schmiedmayer, Emma Brunskill, and James A. Landay. **"GPTCoach: Towards LLM-Based Physical Activity Coaching."** CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '25), (2025). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706598.3713819>
- Liang, Warren, Britney Johnson Mary, Samuel Aidoo, Farinu Hamzah, Adedokun Taofeek, Bamidele Mathew, and Moses Blessing. **"Harnessing Wearable Data and Social Sentiment: Designing Proactive Consumer and Patient Engagement Strategies through Integrated AI Systems."** ResearchGate preprint, June 2025. United States, Nigeria. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393061970>
- Liu, Xin, Yuntao Wang, Sinan Xie, Xiaoyu Zhang, Zixian Ma, Daniel McDuff, and Shwetak Patel. **"MobilePhys: Personalized Mobile Camera-Based Contactless Physiological Sensing."** Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies 6, no. 1 (2022): Article 24. United States, China. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3517225>

- Zhou, Xuyang, Sihui Luo, Yiheng Zhang, Zhiwei Wang, Linsen Song, Yuan Zong, Zeyi Liu, and Min Wu. "**Health-LLM: Large Language Models for Health Prediction via Wearable Sensor Data.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.06866v2*, April 2024. China. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.06866>

C. LLM-driven Health Information Interfaces

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- AI-Generated Health Insights

Use Cases

- Chung, Hyeokgeun, Yeonju Lee, Songye Kim, Namwook Paeng, and Sung Ju Hwang. "**Towards a Personal Health Large Language Model (PH-LLM).**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.06474v1* (2024). South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.06474>

D. Digital Twins for Personal and Population Health

Typical Data Types

- Synthetic and Simulated Health Data
- AI-Generated Health Insights
- In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors

Use Cases

- Albyn Housing Society. "**Fit Homes – Albyn Housing Society.**" *Tech*, 2023. United Kingdom. <https://www.sfha.co.uk/tech/fit-homes-albyn-housing-society>
- Shen, Liang, Zhigang Yang, Xuanyin Liu, Wei Liu, and Yuzhuo Wang. "**From virtual to reality: innovative practices of digital twins in tumor therapy.**" *Journal of Translational Medicine* 23 (2025): 348. China, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-025-06371-z>

E. Knowledge Graphs and Digital Health Libraries

Typical Data Types

- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Online Discussion Forums
- Geospatial Datasets
- Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals

Use Cases

- Correia, Rion Brattig, Jordan C. Rozum, Leonard Cross, Jack Felag, Michael Gallant, Ziqi Guo, Bruce W. Herr II, Aehong Min, Deborah Stungis Rocha, Xuan Wang, Katy Börner, Wendy Miller, and Luis M. Rocha. "**myAURA: Personalized health library for epilepsy management via knowledge graph sparsification and visualization.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.05229v2* (2024). United States, Portugal.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.05229>
- Navarro-Gallinad, Albert, Fabrizio Orlandi, and Declan O'Sullivan. "**Enhancing Rare Disease Research with Semantic Integration of Environmental and Health Data.**" *Proceedings of the 10th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Graphs (IJCKG)*, (2022): 19–27. Ireland.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3502223.3502226>.

4.2 Cross-Cutting Methodological and Ethical Foundations: How research addresses validity, ethics, governance, and infrastructural issues

4.2.1 Methodological and Ethical Foundations of Health Research

A. Data Infrastructure and System Design

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- In-Home Environmental Sensors
- In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors
- In-Home IoT Device Data
- Social Media User-Submitted Content

Use Cases

- Buleje, Italo, Vince S. Siu, Kuan Yu Hsieh, Nigel Hinds, Bing Dang, Erhan Bilal, Thanhnhha Nguyen, Ellen E. Lee, Colin A. Depp, and Jeffrey L. Rogers. **"A Versatile Data Fabric for Advanced IoT-Based Remote Health Monitoring."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.01673v1* (2023). United States. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.01673>
- Burgess, Romana, Alison Boyd, Oliver Davis, Louise A. C. Millard, Mark Mumme, Sarah Robertson, Andy Skinner, Zhuoni Xiao, and Anya Skatova. **"Linking Digital Footprint Data into Longitudinal Population Studies."** *Workshop paper, Digital Footprints Conference 2024* (2024). United Kingdom. <https://digitalfootprintscommunity.org/>
- Dirkson, Anne, Suzan Verberne, Wessel Kraaij, Gerard van Oortmerssen & Hans Gelderblom. **"Automated gathering of real-world data from online patient forums can complement pharmacovigilance for rare cancers."** *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 10317 (2022). Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-13894-8>.
- Ranjan, Yatharth, Jiangeng Chang, Heet Sankesara, Pauline Conde, Zulqarnain Rashid, Richard J. B. Dobson, and Amos Folarin. **"RADAR-IoT: An Open-Source, Interoperable, and Extensible IoT Gateway Framework for Health Research."** *Sensors* 24, no. 14 (2024): 4614. United Kingdom, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24144614>
- Riccio, Piera, Bill Psomas, Francesco Galati, Francisco Escolano, Thomas Hofmann, and Nuria Oliver. **"OpenFilter: A Framework to Democratize Research Access to Social Media AR Filters."** In *Proceedings of the 36th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2022), Track on Datasets and Benchmarks*. Spain, France, Austria, Greece, Switzerland. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.12319>
- Silva Júnior, Paulo Freitas, Jonice Oliveira, and Tiago França. **"CAMEL: Ecosystem for Big Social Data."** In *Proceedings of the XIX Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems (SBSI '23)*, Maceió, Brazil (2023). Brazil. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3592813.3592898>
- Skatova, Anya, and Andy Boyd. **"A protocol for linking participants' retailer 'loyalty card' records into the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)."** *Wellcome Open Research* 8 (2024): 99. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.18900.2>
- Stojchevska, Marija, Mathias De Brouwer, Martijn Courteaux, Bram Steenwinckel, Sofie Van Hoecke, and Femke Ongenaë. **"Unlocking the potential of smartphone and ambient sensors for ADL detection."** *Scientific Reports* 14 (2024): 5392. Belgium. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-56123-0>

- Subramanian, Hemang. **"A Decentralized Marketplace for Patient-Generated Health Data: Design Science Approach."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 25 (2023): e42743. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/42743>
- Sun, Ke, Chunyu Xia, Xinyu Zhang, Hao Chen, and Charlie Jianzhong Zhang. **"Multimodal Daily-Life Logging in Free-living Environment Using Non-Visual Egocentric Sensors on a Smartphone."** *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 8, no. 1 (2024): Article 17. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3643553>
- Tang, Jinzhou. **"Analysis of Decision Support System for Health Resources Based on Intelligent Information Technology."** *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Industrial Control Network and System Engineering Research (ICNSER)*, (2022): 74–78. China. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3556055.3556062>.
- Vuorre, Matti, Kristofer Magnusson, Niklas Johannes, James Butlin, and Andrew K. Przybylski. **"An intensive longitudinal dataset of in-game player behaviour and well-being in PowerWash Simulator."** *Scientific Data* 10, no. 622 (2023). United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02530-3>

B. Measurement Validation and Accuracy

Typical Data Types

- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Synthetic and Simulated Health Data
- In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Online Discussion Forums
- Online Search Behavior

Use Cases

- Chunara, Rumi, Jessica Gjonaj, Eileen Immaculate, Irisa Wang, James Alaro, Lori A. J. Scott-Sheldon, et al. **"Social determinants of health: the need for data science methods and capacity."** *The Lancet Digital Health* 6, no. 4 (2024): e247–e249. United States, Kenya, United Kingdom. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(24\)00037-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(24)00037-2).
- De Choudhury, Munmun. **"Employing Social Media to Improve Mental Health: Pitfalls, Lessons Learned, and the Next Frontier."** *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI '22)* (2022). United States. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3490099.3519389>.

- Di Cara, Nina H., Valerio Maggio, Oliver S. P. Davis, and Claire M. A. Haworth. **"Methodologies for Monitoring Mental Health on Twitter: Systematic Review."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 25 (2023): e42734. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.2196/42734>
- Doherty, Cailbhe, Maximus Baldwin, Alison Keogh, Brian Caulfield, and Rob Argent. **"Keeping Pace with Wearables: A Living Umbrella Review of Systematic Reviews Evaluating the Accuracy of Consumer Wearable Technologies in Health Measurement."** (2024). Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-024-02077-2>
- Downing, Gregory J., Lucas M. Tramontozzi, Jackson Garcia, and Emma Villanueva. **"Harnessing Internet Search Data as a Potential Tool for Medical Diagnosis: Literature Review."** *JMIR Mental Health* 12 (2025): e63149. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/63149>
- Ghosal, Rahul, Marcos Matabuena, and Sujit K. Ghosh. **"Functional Time Transformation Model with Applications to Digital Health."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.19716v1* (2024). United States. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.19716>
- Im, Eunyoung, Sunghoon Kang, and Hyeoneui Kim. **"Development of a Validation and Inspection Tool for Armband-Based Lifelog Data (VITAL) to Facilitate the Clinical Use of Wearable Data: A Prototype and Usability Evaluation."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.14133v1* (2025). South Korea. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.14133>
- Kim, Dae Wook, Minki P. Lee & Daniel B. Forger. **"A Level Set Kalman Filter Approach to Estimate the Circadian Phase and Its Uncertainty from Wearable Data."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.09406v3* (2023). United States. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.09406>
- Owen, David, Adam J. Lynham, Samantha E. Smart, Antonio F. Pardiñas, and Jose Camacho Collados. **"AI for Analyzing Mental Health Disorders Among Social Media Users: Quarter-Century Narrative Review of Progress and Challenges."** *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26 (2024): e59225. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.2196/59225>
- Shim, Jinjoo, Elgar Fleisch & Filipe Barata. **"Circadian rhythm analysis using wearable-based accelerometry as a digital biomarker of aging and healthspan."** *npj Digital Medicine* 7, no. 146 (2024). Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01111-x>.

- Thompson, Matthew, Calvin Chan, Elisabeth Daniels, Kevin Obana, James Taylor, Kate Grailey, Renee Schneider, John Flatley, Viknesh Sounderajah, and Ara Darzi. **"Systematic Review of Health Research Using Internet Search Data."** *Research Square* (2024). United Kingdom and United States.
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4456499/v1>
- Walsh, Lorraine, Alison O'Connor, Patrick Slevin, Rebecca Maguire, and Daniel Kelly. **"Spontaneously generated online patient experience data - how and why is it being used in health research: an umbrella scoping review."** *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 22, no. 1 (2022): 186. United Kingdom, Ireland.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-022-01610-z>
- Yang, Huiyuan, Han Yu, Kusha Sridhar, Thomas Vaessen, Inez Myin-Germeys, and Akane Sano. **"More to Less (M2L): Enhanced Health Recognition in the Wild with Reduced Modality of Wearable Sensors."** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.08267v1* (2022). United States, Belgium.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.08267>
- Zhang, Miao, Salman Rahman, Vishwali Mhasawade, and Rumi Chunara. **"Utilizing Big Data Without Domain Knowledge Impacts Public Health Decision-Making."** *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 121, no. 39 (2024): e2402387121. United States.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2402387121>

C. Ethical Data Practices and Governance

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals
- Social Media User-Submitted Content
- Public Health Surveillance Data
- Geospatial Datasets

Use Cases

- Amutorine, Morine, Neil Lawrence, and Jessica Montgomery. **"Increasing Data Sharing and Use for Social Good: Lessons from Africa's Data-Sharing Practices During the COVID-19 Response."** *Data & Policy* 6 (2024): e53. Kenya, United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2024.43>
- Burgess, Romana, Anya Skatova, and Poppy Taylor. **"Understanding Moderators of Consent Regarding the Sharing of Supermarket Shopping Data in ALSPAC."** *International Journal of Population Data Science* 9, no. 4 (2024): 05. United Kingdom.
<https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v9i4.2419>

- Chen, Kongyang, Dongping Zhang, Sijia Guan, Bing Mi, Jiaying Shen, and Guoqing Wang. "**Private Data Leakage in Federated Human Activity Recognition for Wearable Healthcare Devices.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.10979v2* (2024). China. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.10979>
- Lathan, Hannah Stuart, Amy Kwan, Courtney Takats, Joshua P. Tanner, Rachel Wormer, Diana Romero, and Heidi E. Jones. "**Ethical Considerations and Methodological Uses of Facebook Data in Public Health Research: A Systematic Review.**" *Social Science & Medicine* 322 (2023): 115807. United States. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.115807>

D. Bias, Fairness, and Representativeness

Typical Data Types

- Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking
- Smartphone-Native Sensing
- Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data
- Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals

Use Cases

- Song, Sarah, Madeleine Ashton, Ryan H. Yoo, Zoljargal Lkhagvajav, Roderick Wright, David J. H. Mathews, and Camille O. Taylor. "**Participant Contributions to Person-Generated Health Data Research Using Mobile Devices: Scoping Review.**" *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 27 (2025): e51955. United States. <https://doi.org/10.2196/51955>
- Zhang, Miao, and Rumi Chunara. "**Mitigating Urban-Rural Disparities in Contrastive Representation Learning with Satellite Imagery.**" *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.00550*, September 2024. United States. <https://arxiv.org/html/2211.08672v3>

Supply: Social Data Sources for Health and Wellbeing Research

In this section we map social data sources relevant for health and wellbeing research. We identify data sources that could support future research, and we note where current research focus areas already draw on these types of data. We organize the taxonomy around eight domains of social data sources:

1. [Communication and Social Interaction Data](#): resulting from communicating and engaging in social interactions - for pleasure, study and/or work (8 subtypes)
2. [Mobility and Geolocation Data](#): resulting from having people and products moving around (11 subtypes)
3. [Health and Wellness Tracking Data](#): resulting from health tracking, support, and documentation (8 subtypes)
4. [Environmental and Infrastructure Data](#): resulting from managing natural assets, infrastructure, and the built environment (11 subtypes)
5. [Financial and Consumption Data](#): resulting from consumption, commercial and financial transactions (5 subtypes)
6. [In-Home and IoT Sensor Data](#): resulting from home assistance and other in-home, IoT, sensor devices (6 subtypes)
7. [Media and Entertainment Data](#): resulting from media and entertainment consumption (4 subtypes)
8. [Work, Education, and Skill Data](#): resulting from obtaining an (ongoing) education and job experience (2 subtypes)

For each data type, this section provides:

- A concise description
- Typical actors involved in its collection or access
- Whether it contains or may reveal personally identifiable information (PII)
- Whether it is structured, unstructured, or semi-structured
- The types of metadata typically captured
- Whether its use in health research requires re-use of data originally collected for other purposes
- Focus areas which often draw on this data type, based on the taxonomy presented in the previous section

1. Communication and Social Interaction Data

1.1 Social Media User-Submitted Content

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Social Media User-Submitted Content	Posts, likes, comments, hashtags, polls, photos, and videos intentionally created and shared by users.	Social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, TikTok, Sina Weibo)	Y	US	Location, Time, Language, Device	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy • Mental Health Expression and Peer Support Online • Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks

1.2 Social Media Networks and Architectures

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Social Media Networks and Architectures	Data about the structure and dynamics of social platforms, including user relationships (e.g., friendship graphs, follower and interaction networks, contact lists), derived network indicators (e.g., Social Connectedness Index), and the organization of activity over time (e.g., profile timelines).	Social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, TikTok, Sina Weibo)	Y	S	Account ID, Connection Degree, Location (inferred)	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy

1.3 Social Media Metadata

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Social Media Metadata	Metadata associated with social media content which is itself used for health research, such as content format, creator identity, and platform type.	Social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, TikTok, Sina Weibo)	Y	SS	N/A	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy

1.4 Online Discussion Forums

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Online Discussion Forums	User-generated posts and comments on public or semi-public community forums.	Forum platforms (e.g., Reddit, Inspire, WebMD, Zhihu)	Y	US	Username, Timestamp, Thread ID, Topic Tags	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mental Health Expression and Peer Support Online

1.5 Blogs and Microblogs

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Blogs and Microblogs	Public-facing, user-generated or curated content on blogs, vlogs, and microblogging platforms.	Online platforms including Twitter, Medium, YouTube, and Reddit	Potentially identifiable	US	Timestamp, Author Handle, Language, Platform Type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy

1.6 Text/SMS and Peer-to-peer Messages

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Text/SMS and Peer-to-peer Messages	Private communication records including SMS, messaging apps, or workplace chat logs.	Messaging platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Slack), Telecom providers	Y	US	Message count, Word count, Number of contacts, Timestamp	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing

1.7 LLM-Enabled and Conversational Agent Interaction Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
LLM-Enabled and Conversational Agent Interaction Data	User inputs and system outputs from interactions with conversational systems, whether session-level or aggregated. Covers LLMs, chatbot-based tools across text, voice, and multimodal interfaces.	App developers, clinical researchers, healthcare providers, chatbot developers.	Y	SS/US	User ID, timestamp, Prompt Length, tool version, language.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI-Augmented Health Interfaces and Knowledge Systems

1.8 Online search behavior

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Online search behavior	Search trends and history, keyword frequency, query patterns, and behavioral signals captured from search engines or platforms with embedded search functions.	Search platforms (e.g., Google, Bing, Baidu, YouTube)	N	US	Query Text, Timestamp, Location, Device Type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suicidal Ideation and Crisis Detection Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks Public Perception, Stigma, and Health Literacy

2. Mobility and Geolocation Data

2.1 Smartphone location tracking

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smartphone location tracking	GPS-based and network-based (Wi-Fi, cell tower) location data passively collected via smartphones.	Mobile OS providers, app developers, telecom operators	Y	S	Location, Timestamp, Device ID, App Name	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety • Place-Based and Structural Factors • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities • Evacuation Patterns and Shelter Coordination

2.2 Transportation mode detection

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Transportation mode detection	Inferred modes of transportation (walking, biking, driving, public transport, air travel) derived from smartphone sensors, app algorithms, and aviation data.	Mobile OS providers, navigation apps, transportation apps	Y	S	Location, Timestamp, Device ID, Mode Type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities

2.3 Crowdsourced mobile app data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Crowdsourced mobile app data	User-submitted mobility data or passively sensed mobility from crowdsourced apps (e.g., traffic, disaster response, event apps).	App providers, navigation platforms	Y	S/US	Location, Timestamp, Route, Speed	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Warning via Social Sensing • Disaster Response and Recovery

2.4 Telecom mobility data (CDRs)

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Telecom mobility data (CDRs)	Aggregated mobile phone network records capturing user movements between cell towers	Telecom operators	Y	S/US	Tower ID, Timestamp, Anonymized User	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities • Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks

2.5 App-based location & app usage patterns

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
App-based location & app usage patterns	Location behavior linked with app interaction data (e.g., mobility apps, shopping apps, food environment apps).	App providers, data brokers	Y	SS	Location, Timestamp, App name, Device ID	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial and Socioeconomic Disparities in Access • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities

2.6 QR code-based mobility interactions

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
QR code-based mobility interactions	Location-based check-ins and mobility traces captured via QR code scans (e.g., event attendance, contact tracing).	Event organizers, public health agencies	Y	S	Location, Timestamp, Device ID	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaster Response and Recovery

2.7 Traffic and transport flow data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Traffic and transport flow data	Aggregated vehicle traffic flow, congestion data from third-party services (e.g., INRIX, Waze). or public sources	Traffic analytics companies Insurance companies City governments	Y	NS	Location, Timestamp, Traffic flow, Speed	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early Warning via Social Sensing Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety

2.8 GPS trajectory data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
GPS trajectory data	Device-recorded movement trajectories for individuals or vehicles, including wearables, vehicle sensors, bike-sharing, ride-hailing, and aircraft (e.g., OpenSky Network flight tracking).	App providers, micromobility operators, vehicle telematics companies	Y	S	Location, Timestamp, Device ID	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities • Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety

2.9 Bluetooth signal data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Bluetooth signal data	Proximity-based location tracking using Bluetooth beacons (e.g., micromobility validation, indoor navigation).	Mobile phone manufacturers, venue operators, app developers	Y	S	Timestamp, Beacon ID, Device ID, Proximity Strength	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety

2.10 Platform-based aggregated mobility data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Platform-based aggregated mobility data	Aggregated mobility patterns derived from user location data on digital platforms (e.g., Facebook Crisis Mobility Data, Meta colocation data, Google Mobility Reports).	Social media platforms, search platforms, tech companies	N	S	Timestamp, aggregated origin-destination flows, Density maps, Geographic units	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks • Pandemic Preparedness and Behavioral Modeling • Place-Based and Structural Factors • Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities

2.11 Software Development Kit (SDK) Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Software Development Kit (SDK) Data	Location and usage data collected via SDKs embedded in smartphone apps, using device sensors like GPS, Bluetooth, and Wi-Fi. Can be collected by app developers or aggregated from third-party data brokers.	App developers, data brokers, telecom providers	Y	S	Location, Timestamp, Device ID, App Name, App Usage Patterns	Y	

3. Health and Wellness Tracking Data

3.1 Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Wearable-Derived Physiological Signals	Physiological signals captured by wearable sensors, including cardiovascular, respiratory, skin conductance, and multimodal physiological profiles (e.g., heart rate, HRV, SpO2, ECG, EDA, respiration, blood volume pulse, skin temperature, seizure detection).	Wearable device manufacturers, health researchers, app developers, clinical trial sponsor	Y	S	Device ID, timestamp, sampling rate, sensor calibration, body location		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Chronic Disease Monitoring and Management • Methodological and Ethical Foundations of Health Research • AI-Augmented Health Interfaces and Knowledge Systems • Infectious Disease Surveillance and Outbreak Response

3.2 Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data	Behavioral data from wearables related to physical activity and sleep, including step count, gait, exercise time, calorie burn, sleep stages, circadian rhythms, and AI-derived activity and sleep profiles.	Wearable device manufacturers, fitness platforms, health researchers, insurers, public health entities.	Y	S	Device ID, timestamp, time zone, activity type, sleep/wake markers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Neurological Conditions • Post-Surgical Recovery and Rehabilitation • Personalized Coaching and Prediction Systems

3.3 Wearable-Derived Contextual and Environmental Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Wearable-Derived Activity and Sleep Data	Environmental and contextual signals captured by wearables (e.g., ambient light, sound, proximity, synchrony).	Wearable device manufacturers, HCI researchers, behavioral health researchers.	Y	SS	Device ID, timestamp, environmental condition, location (if used).	Environmental and contextual signals captured by wearables (e.g., ambient light, sound, proximity, synchrony).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wearable device manufacturers, HCI researchers, behavioral health researchers.

3.4 Smartphone-Native Sensing

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smartphone-Native Sensing	Data derived from smartphone-integrated sensors and system capabilities (e.g., microphone, camera, inertial sensors, Wi-Fi, light/proximity sensors), including multimodal sensing (e.g., camera-based PPG, screen interaction patterns, keyboard dynamics, phone usage patterns).	App developers, health researchers, smartphone manufacturers, clinical trial sponsors.	Y	S/SS	Device ID, location, timestamp, sensor state, app version, OS version.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Data Infrastructure and System Design • Early Warning via Social Sensing • Tobacco, Alcohol, and Drug Use Detection

3.4 Smartphone-Native Sensing

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smartphone-Native Sensing	Data derived from smartphone-integrated sensors and system capabilities (e.g., microphone, camera, inertial sensors, Wi-Fi, light/proximity sensors), including multimodal sensing (e.g., camera-based PPG, screen interaction patterns, keyboard dynamics, phone usage patterns).	App developers, health researchers, smartphone manufacturers, clinical trial sponsors.	Y	S/SS	Device ID, location, timestamp, sensor state, app version, OS version.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Health and Emotional Wellbeing • Data Infrastructure and System Design • Early Warning via Social Sensing • Tobacco, Alcohol, and Drug Use Detection

3.5 Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smartphone App-Based Health Tracking	Data entered or tracked in smartphone apps for health monitoring (e.g., symptom trackers, sleep apps, food diaries, EMA surveys).	App developers, health researchers, wellness platforms, healthcare providers.	Y	S/SS	User ID, timestamp, app version, device metadata.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical Data Practices and Governance • Spatial and Socioeconomic Disparities in Access • Relapse Prediction and Intervention • Obesity, Diabetes, and Metabolic Health

3.6 Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Recorded Experience and Self-Reported Data	Structured or unstructured self-report data on user experience, symptoms, and health status, collected via apps, surveys, forms, diaries, or forums. This includes both standardized instruments (e.g., patient-reported outcomes like NeuroQoL) and free-text or diary-style entries. Also includes human-coded or machine-analyzed annotations of observed or recorded behavior, including audiovisual recordings.	App developers, researchers, public health agencies, community platforms	Y	S/SS/US	User ID, timestamp, survey metadata, context tags.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age-Specific Applications (Children, Elderly) • Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety • ADHD and Behavioral Disorders

3.7 AI-Generated Health Insights

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
AI-Generated Health Insights	AI/ML/LLM-generated outputs including predictions, risk scores, personalized recommendations, symptom extraction.	App developers, health tech firms, clinical researchers, healthcare providers.	Y	S/SS	Model version, timestamp, source data type, confidence score, feature set used.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research from and about health equity in LMICs (Low- and Middle-Income Countries) Tobacco, Alcohol, and Drug Use Detection Digital Twins for Personal and Population Health

3.8 Synthetic and Simulated Health Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Synthetic and Simulated Health Data	Simulated data generated to represent user health trajectories or wearable/sensor data, including virtual patient data and GAN-based synthetic health records.	ML/AI researchers, simulation scientists, app developers, healthcare data companies.	N	S	Generation algorithm/version, scenario metadata, intended population, source template.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalized Coaching and Prediction Systems Digital Twins for Personal and Population Health

4. Environmental and Infrastructure Data

4.1 Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Synthetic and Simulated Health Data	Simulated data generated to represent user health trajectories or wearable/sensor data, including virtual patient data and GAN-based synthetic health records.	ML/AI researchers, simulation scientists, app developers, healthcare data companies.	N	S	Generation algorithm/version, scenario metadata, intended population, source template.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalized Coaching and Prediction Systems Digital Twins for Personal and Population Health

4.2 Air, Sound, and Atmospheric Sensor Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Water and Wastewater Sensor Data	Data from sensors monitoring water quality and wastewater (including aircraft wastewater).	Enviro agencies, utilities, public health departments, research consortia.	N	S	Timestamp, Location, Sensor, Measurement units, Sampling protocol	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks

4.3 Disaster and Hazard Sensor Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Disaster and Hazard Sensor Data	Data from sensors monitoring natural hazards such as floods, seismic activity, landslides.	Environmental agencies, emergency management, local governments, private sector operators.	N	S	Timestamp, Location, Sensor type, Hazard type, Measurement units, Event ID.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Warning via Social Sensing

4.4 Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data	Satellite-based imagery and remote sensing data (optical, thermal, radar, multispectral), used to map land cover, infrastructure, hazards, and environmental change.	Government space agencies, satellite companies, international NGOs, research institutions	N	S/SS/US	Timestamp, Geolocation, Sensor type, Spatial resolution, Processing level, Satellite ID	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pandemic Preparedness and Behavioral Modeling • Air Quality, Pollution, and Health • Research from and about health equity in LMICs (Low- and Middle-Income Countries)

4.5 Geospatial datasets

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Geospatial datasets	Spatial datasets describing the built environment, infrastructure, land use, population context, and environmental exposures. Includes walkability networks, zoning, public transport networks, GIS shapefiles.	Government agencies, satellite companies, research institutions, international NGOs	N	S	Timestamp, Location, Feature type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Place-Based and Structural Factors Evacuation Patterns and Shelter Coordination Nutrition, Food Security, and Consumption Surveillance Knowledge Graphs and Digital Health Libraries

4.6 Street-level imagery data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Street-level imagery data	Images of roads, sidewalks, and urban spaces captured by platforms (e.g., Google Street View, drone imagery, geolocated photos).	Mapping platforms, research institutions	Potentially	US	Image metadata (location, timestamp), Image ID	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transportation, Mobility, Walkability, Pedestrian Safety Place-Based and Structural Factors

4.7 Mapping Platform and Crowdsourced Mapping Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Mapping Platform and Crowdsourced Mapping Data	Open-source and commercial mapping data (e.g., OpenStreetMap, Leaflet) and crowdsourced mapping of environmental conditions, disasters, and infrastructure disruptions	Open data communities, app developers, navigation providers, citizen science groups, emergency response organizations	N	S	Location, Timestamp, Map feature metadata, Contributor metadata (if applicable), Event tags	N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaster Response and Recovery

4.8 Smart City Camera and Sensor Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smart City Camera and Sensor Data	Data streams from smart city surveillance cameras, traffic cameras, and thermal pedestrian imaging systems	City governments, transit authorities, commercial operators, research institutions	Potentially	S/SS	Location, Timestamp, Sensor ID, Camera metadata, Object detection labels.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age-Specific Applications (Children, Elderly) Disaster Response and Recovery

4.9 Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Platform-Derived Environmental and Infrastructure Signals	Signals related to environmental conditions or infrastructure status derived from public-facing digital platforms, including search trends (e.g., Google Health Trends), citizen science app data (e.g., Smoke Sense), and social media posts reporting air quality, smoke, pollen, disaster conditions, or infrastructure disruptions	Public health agencies, research institutions, citizen science communities, digital platform providers, emergency management agencies	Potentially	S/SS/US	Timestamp, Location, Platform type, Content label or keyword, User metadata (if available), Engagement metrics	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air Quality, Pollution, and Health • Disaster Response and Recovery • Knowledge Graphs and Digital Health Libraries

4.10 Built Environment Simulation and Digital Twin Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Built Environment Simulation and Digital Twin Data	Simulation outputs and digital twins of the built environment and infrastructure systems (e.g., 3D city models, disaster response models)	City governments, research consortia, digital twin developers, planning agencies	N	S/SS	Timestamp, Location, simulation parameters, Model version, Scenario metadata	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Twins for Personal and Population Health

4.11 Legal and Justice System Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Legal and Justice System Data	Data from court records, legal proceedings, judicial rulings, prison and correctional facilities, legal aid services, and other justice-related sources relevant to public health.	Judicial bodies, legal aid organizations, NGOs, ministries of justice, researchers, public health agencies	Potentially	S/SS	Case ID, Court type, Date, Geographic jurisdiction, Legal issue type, Outcome, Demographics (if public), Document type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marginalized Communities and Health Disparities

5. Financial and Consumption Data

5.1 Shopping data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Shopping Data	Data on individual purchasing behavior, including retail transactions, loyalty card purchases, voucher redemptions, and aggregated commercial transactions.	Retailers, payment processors, loyalty program operators, data brokers, marketing firms	Potentially	S	Timestamp, Store/location, Product category, Quantity, Price, Loyalty ID (if applicable), Payment method.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition, Food Security, and Consumption Surveillance • Advertising, Marketing, and Behavioral Health Risks • Spatial and Socioeconomic Disparities in Access

5.2 Aggregated Consumer and Marketing Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Aggregated Consumer and Marketing Data	Aggregated consumer profiles and marketing datasets including demographic segments, brand preferences, purchase frequency, and modeled behavior patterns. Often derived from third-party brokers.	Data brokers, marketing platforms, advertisers, analytics firms	Potentially	S/SS	Demographic segment, Geographic unit (postal code, census tract), Behavioral profile, Purchase categories, Aggregation method.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition, Food Security, and Consumption Surveillance • Advertising, Marketing, and Behavioral Health Risks

5.3 Financial Transaction Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Financial Transaction Data	Banking and financial transaction data reflecting broader consumer spending patterns, including debit/credit card transactions and account activity	Banks, financial institutions, fintech companies, data aggregators	Y	S	Timestamp, Merchant category, Transaction amount, Location, Account type, Transaction type.	Y	

5.4 Online Product Review and Retail Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Online Product Review and Retail Data	Consumer-generated content and product data from online platforms, including product reviews (e.g., Amazon, WebMD), grocery product data scraped from online retailers, and food environment data from review platforms (e.g., Yelp)	E-commerce platforms, review sites, data scraping services, health researchers	Potentially	S/SS/US	Product ID, Review text, Rating, Timestamp, Reviewer metadata (if available), Store/site metadata.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vaccination Sentiment and Misinformation Spread

5.5 App-Based Food and Consumption Tracking Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
App-Based Food and Consumption Tracking Data	Self-reported and app-tracked data on personal consumption behaviors, including food diary apps (e.g., MyFitnessPal), and apps tracking store visits, deal searches, or purchase intent (e.g., Flipp).	App developers, health platforms, wellness companies, researchers	Y	S/SS	Timestamp, Food item, Portion size, Nutrients, App usage patterns, Location (if applicable), Store visit data	Y	

6. In-Home and IoT Sensor Data

6.1 In-Home Environmental Sensors

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
In-Home Environmental Sensors	Data from sensors capturing indoor environmental conditions such as air quality, temperature, humidity, light levels, noise, and power consumption	Smart home device makers, app developers, researchers, DIY IoT communities	Potentially	S	Timestamp, Location, Sensor type, Measurement units.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Infrastructure and System Design

6.2 In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
In-Home Health and Behavioral Sensors	Sensor data from the home environment that captures health, physiological signals (e.g., heart rate, ECG, oxygen levels), movement, sleep, and behavior. Includes ambient sensors and in-home wearables.	Healthcare providers, device makers, telehealth platforms, researchers.	Y	S	Timestamp, Sensor type, Parameter, Device ID, User ID.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Neurological Conditions Measurement Validation and Accuracy

6.3 In-Home Safety and Assistance Sensors

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
In-Home Safety and Assistance Sensors	Data from sensors supporting home safety (e.g., presence, contact, appliance use, fall detection, bed sensors).	Aging-in-place providers, health tech companies, researchers.	Potentially	S/SS	Timestamp, Location, Sensor type, Event type.	Y	

6.4 In-Home IoT Device Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
In-Home IoT Device Data	Usage and operational data from home-based IoT devices and control apps, including smart appliance usage, energy management systems, lighting, HVAC controls, and DIY-style IoT-enabled solutions.	Smart home companies, app developers, utilities, researchers.	Potentially	S/SS	Timestamp, Device ID, Event type, Control state.	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cardiovascular and Blood Pressure Monitoring • Data Infrastructure and System Design • Respiratory Conditions

6.5 In-Home Voice Assistants and Conversational Interfaces

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
In-Home Voice Assistants and Conversational Interfaces	Interaction data from voice-controlled home assistants (e.g., Alexa, Google Home).	Voice assistant platforms, app developers, researchers	Y	SS/US	Timestamp, Command text/audio, Response, Device ID.	Y	

6.6 Smart Home-Linked Energy Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Smart Home-Linked Energy Data	Energy use data from smart home devices and smart grid platforms	Utilities, smart home firms, app developers, researchers	Potentially	S	Timestamp, Device ID, Energy use, Appliance type.	Y	

7. Media and Entertainment Data

7.1 Media Content Consumption Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Media Content Consumption Data	Data on user interactions with media content, including video and audio streams, viewing patterns, search trends, and content engagement on platforms such as YouTube, Twitch, TikTok, and streaming services.	Streaming services, social media platforms, gaming companies, researchers	Potentially	S/SS	Timestamp, Content ID, User ID (if available), Engagement type (view, like, comment), Session duration, Platform type	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ADHD and Behavioral Disorders

7.2 News Media and News Content Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
News Media and News Content Data	Content and metadata from news media sources, including articles, headlines, sentiment, tone, and coverage trends	News aggregators, media monitoring firms, public health agencies, researchers	Potentially	S/SS/US	Timestamp, Source, Headline/text, Language, Sentiment, Topic, Geographic tagging	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Warning Systems for Disease Outbreaks • Disaster Response and Recovery

7.3 Game and Interactive Media Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Game and Interactive Media Data	Data on user interactions with games and interactive media platforms, including gameplay telemetry, behavioral features, session data, and associated media (e.g., video/audio recordings)	Gaming companies, app developers, researchers	Potentially	S/SS	Timestamp, User ID, Game ID, Session duration, Interaction events, Content recordings	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depression, Loneliness, and Mental Wellbeing • ADHD and Behavioral Disorders

7.4 Crowdsourced Media Content and Annotations

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Crowdsourced Media Content and Annotations	Media-related content or annotations generated by human contributors, such as crowd worker labels of sentiment, relevance, or topic in media content	Crowdsourcing platforms, researchers, media organizations	Potentially	S/SS/US	Timestamp, Annotator ID, Annotation type, Content ID, Aggregation level	Y	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ADHD and Behavioral Disorders Vaccination Sentiment and Misinformation Spread

8. Work, Education, and Skill Data

8.1 Professional Networking Platform Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Professional Networking Platform Data	Data from professional networking platforms (e.g., LinkedIn), including profiles, employment history, job titles, industry sectors, skills endorsements, and professional connections	Professional networking platforms, researchers, public health agencies	Y	S/SS	Timestamp, Profile ID, Employment history, Job title, Industry sector, Skills, Connection network	Y	

8.2 Online Learning Platform Data

Data Type	Description	Typical Actors	Includes PII?	Data Structure	Typical Metadata	Requires Re-Use?	Typical Focus Areas
Online Learning Platform Data	Data from online learning platforms (e.g., Coursera, Udemy), including course enrollments, completions, progress, skills acquired, and certification status	Online learning platforms, researchers, workforce development agencies	Y	S	Timestamp, User ID, Course ID, Progress, Completion status, Certification data	Y	

Data Services

Alongside new forms of data and research use cases, a growing ecosystem of services and infrastructure providers is emerging to support the use of social data in health and wellbeing research. These services help researchers access, manage, and analyze social datasets, build technical capacity, and navigate legal and ethical considerations. In this section, we catalog the **86 social data services** identified through our review. For each, we provide its name, location, website, stated purpose, core functions, and funding model.

All of Us Research Program

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure
- **Data Types:** Crowdsourced genetic and health data
- **Funding Sources:** United States Government (NIH)
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://allofus.nih.gov/>
- **Notable Features:** One of the largest and most diverse health databases; supports precision medicine

Apple Health Records

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Health records, lab results, medications, vitals
- **Funding Sources:** Apple Inc.
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.apple.com/healthcare/health-records/>
- **Notable Features:** Enables users to download and view their health records directly on their iPhone and share with authorized third-parties; supports over 12,000 care locations; secure device-level data storage

AUSSDA – The Austrian Social Science Data Archive

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Capacity Building, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social science research data
- **Funding Sources:** National funding
- **Location:** Austria
- **Website:** <https://aussda.at/>

- **Notable Features:** National node for CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives)

BlueDot

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Geospatial data, health data, social media data
- **Funding Sources:** Venture capital (Horizon Ventures, BDC Capital)
- **Location:** Canada
- **Website:** <https://bluedot.global/>
- **Notable Features:** AI-driven outbreak surveillance; proprietary platform; detected COVID-19 before WHO alert

China Kadoorie Biobank (CKB)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Demographic, lifestyle, physical measures, blood biomarkers, genetic data, morbidity and mortality records, environmental data

- **Funding Sources:** Kadoorie Charitable Foundation in Hong Kong, Wellcome Trust, Chinese Natural Science Foundation and Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology, UK MRC, British Heart Foundation and Cancer Research UK

- **Location:** China, United Kingdom

- **Website:** <https://www.ckbiobank.org/>

- **Notable Features:** Large-scale prospective cohort study tracking over 512,000 Chinese adults to investigate chronic disease causes. Provides secure access for approved researchers worldwide.

Ciitizen

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Medical records, genomic data, patient-reported data
- **Funding Sources:** VC-backed (Andreessen Horowitz, Verily, Section 32)
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.ciitizen.com/>

- **Notable Features:** Patient-controlled data sharing; AI-generated health profiles; focused on rare and complex diseases

Colorado Longitudinal Study (COLS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Crowdsourced clinical and health data
- **Funding Sources:** Grants, individual donations
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://colostudy.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Nonprofit biobank; open to external researchers; participant-led data contribution

Consumer Data Research Centre

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Consumption, education, mobility, transportation, IoT data
- **Funding Sources:** UK Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)
- **Location:** United Kingdom

- **Website:** <https://www.cdrc.ac.uk/>

- **Notable Features:** Accelerates social sciences research using consumer data, publishes "data stories" showcasing research impact, offers tutorials and training on data use and methods

Croatian Social Science Data Archive (CROSSDA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social science research data
- **Funding Sources:** Croatian Ministry of Science and Education
- **Location:** Croatia
- **Website:** <https://www.crossda.hr/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; supports full research data lifecycle

Czech Social Science Data Archive (ČSDA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Preservation

- **Data Types:** Social science research data
- **Funding Sources:** Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
- **Location:** Czech Republic
- **Website:** <https://archiv.soc.cas.cz/cz/>
- **Notable Features:** National node of CESSDA; supports secondary analysis and comparative survey participation

Dalberg Data Insights (DDI)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Mobile phone data, satellite imagery, financial and health data
- **Funding Sources:** Dalberg Group, with partners including telecom operators and public institution
- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://dalberg.com/what-we-do/dalberg-data-insights/>
- **Notable Features:** Builds inclusive data ecosystems, develops AI/ML tools, supports organizational data strategies

DATICE (GAGNÍS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Survey data, interviews, registrations, focus groups
- **Funding Sources:** Ministry of Education and Children, University of Iceland
- **Location:** Iceland
- **Website:** <https://datice.is/en>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; hosts Nordic Data Stewardship Network

Data Archive Social Sciences Italy (DASSI)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Quantitative social science data, metadata, national statistics
- **Funding Sources:** Italian National Research Council (CNR), University of Milano-Bicocca
- **Location:** Italy
- **Website:** <https://www.unidata.unimib.it/?lang=en>

- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; supports reuse of national/international survey data

Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) Data Station Life Sciences

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Capacity building, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social sciences, humanities, archaeology, life sciences, physical sciences
- **Funding Sources:** Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), Dutch Research Council (NWO)
- **Location:** Netherlands
- **Website:** <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/life-sciences/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Provides a secure platform to deposit and publish life sciences datasets, supports customizable licenses and access restrictions

Data Biosphere

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Biomedical, genomic, clinical data

- **Funding Sources:** Broad Institute, Verily Life Sciences, various universities

- **Location:** United States

- **Website:** <https://www.databiosphere.org/>

- **Notable Features:** Develops modular, interoperable components for managing, analyzing, and sharing biomedical data, collaboratively develops data standards

Data Centre Serbia for Social Sciences (DCS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Service Provision

- **Data Types:** Multidisciplinary social science data (e.g. economics, education, health, political science)

- **Funding Sources:** International funds (e.g. SEEDS, CESSDA SaW), Institute of Economic Sciences

- **Location:** Serbia

- **Website:** <https://datacentarserbia.com/>

- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; archive in development; hosted at IES Belgrade

Data to Policy Navigator

- **Primary Functions:** Service provision, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Healthcare data repositories
- **Funding Sources:** BMZ, EU, supported by GIZ
- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://www.datatopolicy.org/repository>
- **Notable Features:** Provides a repository of use cases demonstrating how data can inform policy outcomes, offers resources and tools to support effective data use in policymaking, builds a network for policymakers aiming to advance data-driven decision-making

Datavant

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Healthcare and insurance data
- **Funding Sources:** Series B funding from Johnson & Johnson Innovation, Cigna Ventures and others
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.datavant.com/about>

- **Notable Features:** Health data exchange network, 60M+ records enabled, robust network and data security tools

Data Zetu

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Community health and socio-economic indicators, geospatial data
- **Funding Sources:** PEPFAR, MCC (DCLI program)
- **Location:** Tanzania
- **Website:** <https://datazetu.dlab.or.tz/>
- **Notable Features:** Empowers communities to make better decisions, conducts hyperlocal listening campaigns, collaborates with artists and others to provide training, tools, geospatial data.

Development Gateway

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Health, agriculture, education, finance, procurement data
- **Funding Sources:** World Bank (initial), project-specific funding from various donors

- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://developmentgateway.org/expertise/health/>
- **Notable Features:** Designs and deploys data systems and digital tools to improve access and usability, researches barriers and solutions, delivers training and advisory services to build institutional capacity; key programs include youth and tobacco data initiatives in Africa

Digital Dog

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Service provision, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** User engagement, mental health assessments, anonymized feedback
- **Funding Sources:** Black Dog Institute
- **Location:** Australia
- **Website:** <http://digitaldog.org.au/>
- **Notable Features:** Mobile and online tools for mental health, research into effectiveness of digital intervention, training for clinical integration

Empatica

- **Primary Functions:** Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Physiological data, sleep and activity metrics
- **Funding Sources:** Empatica inc.
- **Location:** United States and Italy
- **Website:** <https://www.empatica.com/en-eu/rawdata/>
- **Notable Features:** MIT Media Lab spinoff company providing wearables and AI tools for real-time health monitoring and raw sensor data for clinical research.

Ethica Data

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Smartphone and wearables data
- **Funding Sources:**
- **Location:** Canada
- **Website:** <https://www.cengn.ca/project/case-studies/ethica-data/>

- **Notable Features:** No-code platform for health research and clinical trials. It allows researchers to build apps that integrate surveys, cognitive tasks, and passive sensor data, enabling scalable, resource-efficient human-subject research

European Network of Trusted Research Environments

- **Primary Functions:** Service provision
- **Data Types:** Trusted research environment data sharing
- **Funding Sources:** EU Horizon Europe Programme
- **Location:** Europe
- **Website:** <https://eosc-entrust.eu/about>
- **Notable Features:** Cross-country TRE alignment, shared standards for secure data access

EUDAT

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Service provision, Preservation
- **Data Types:**
- **Funding Sources:** Membership subscriptions of the Collaborative Data Infrastructure members; European Commission (EU)

- **Location:** Finland
- **Website:** <https://www.eudat.eu/>
- **Notable Features:** Provides services for data storage, preservation, and sharing (e.g. B2SAFE, B2SHARE, B2FIND); established collaborative infrastructure for open science across Europe

Financial Data Service

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** De-identified banking and finance data
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI's Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.sdruk.ukri.org/2025/01/20/new-financial-and-energy-data-services/>
- **Notable Features:** Provides secure access to de-identified banking and financial data; supports research on economic resilience, inclusion, and policy

Finnish Social and Health Data Permit Authority (Findata)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research

- **Data Types:** Social welfare and health data
- **Funding Sources:** Ministry of Social Affairs and Health
- **Location:** Finland
- **Website:** <https://findata.fi/en/>
- **Notable Features:** Central authority for secondary use of health data; issues permits, compiles data, and supports secure analysis environments

Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Quantitative and qualitative social science data
- **Funding Sources:** University of Tampere, Academy of Finland
- **Location:** Finland
- **Website:** <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/fi/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; hosts Aila and Loda portals; Offers English metadata and research method guides

GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building, Research
- **Data Types:** Quantitative social science, survey, and longitudinal data
- **Funding Sources:** German Federal Ministry of Education and Research
- **Location:** Germany
- **Website:** <https://www.gesis.org/home>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Supports entire research data cycle

Geographic Data Service

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Geospatial, administrative data
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI's Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://geods.ac.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** Provides integrated spatial datasets with tiered access; supports research on geographic inequality, policy, and mobility

GIZ Data Lab

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Social media, geospatial, crowdsourced behavioral, AI-generated data
- **Funding Sources:** GIZ, BMZ
- **Location:** Germany/Global
- **Website:**
<https://www.giz.de/expertise/html/61847.html>
- **Notable Features:** Prototypes AI and data-driven development solutions; builds ethical and effective data capacity with partners

Google COVID-19 Community Mobility Reports

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research
- **Data Types:** Mobility data
- **Funding Sources:** Google
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:**
<https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/?hl=en>

- **Notable Features:** Provides anonymized reports on movement trends during COVID-19; public and geographically segmented data

Google Health

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure
- **Data Types:** Health and wellness data, smart device data, online behavior data
- **Funding Sources:** Google
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://health.google/>
- **Notable Features:** Develops AI-driven digital health tools; offers public datasets on mobility and healthcare access

Health Data Collaborative (HDC)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Clinical, digital, and community health data
- **Funding Sources:** Multi-stakeholder; includes over 400 partners

- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://www.healthdatacollaborative.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Coordinates partners to strengthen country health data systems; promotes alignment with SDG targets

Healthcare Data Institute (HDI)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity building, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Health data
- **Funding Sources:** Membership contributions
- **Location:** France
- **Website:** <https://healthcaredatainstitute.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Hosts events and publishes research on topics like AI in healthcare; advises policymakers and industry on data use

HealthDataSharing.org

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Health and medical data, social determinants data

- **Funding Sources:** Patient Centered Outcomes Research Institute
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://healthdatasharing.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Publishes expert roundtable outputs and tools to support ethical and effective data sharing practices

Healthy and Sustainable Places Data Service (HASP)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Transport, retail, business, and infrastructure data
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI's Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.sdruk.ukri.org/2025/01/15/new-era-in-health-and-sustainability-research/>
- **Notable Features:** Supports research on mobility, health, and local economies with integrated datasets; accessible to accredited researchers

HIE of One

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** EHRs, wearable device data, personal health data
- **Funding Sources:** Open-source, community-based initiative
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://hieofone.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Develops decentralized patient-controlled health data sharing systems; uses open-source protocols for interoperability, consent, authorization

Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Geospatial and response data across crises
- **Funding Sources:** UN OCHA
- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://data.humdata.org/>

- **Notable Features:** Hosts 18,000+ datasets for humanitarian response; offers CKAN-based open API

Imagery Data Service (Imago)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Satellite, geospatial, environmental, urban imagery data
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI's Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://imago.ac.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** Creates research-ready satellite imagery datasets; tools and resources for environmental and health applications

Innovations for Poverty Action – Health & Nutrition

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Health utilization, nutrition, maternal and disease data
- **Funding Sources:** NIH, World Bank, foundations
- **Location:** Global (20+ countries)

- **Website:** <https://poverty-action.org/health-nutrition>
- **Notable Features:** Runs RCTs to assess intervention effectiveness and shares findings to inform policy; over 100 evaluations in health and nutrition

International COVID-19 Data Alliance (ICODA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** COVID-19 clinical, genomic, epidemiological, service delivery data
- **Funding Sources:** COVID-19 Therapeutics Accelerator Program, Gates Foundation, Minderoo, Microsoft AI for Health
- **Location:** Global
- **Website:** <https://icoda-research.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Provides a secure data platform; supports 12+ COVID-related research projects and facilitates data access

Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Quantitative social science datasets

- **Funding Sources:** University College Dublin
- **Location:** Ireland
- **Website:** <https://www.ucd.ie/issda/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node

Lelapa AI

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity building, Service provision
- **Data Types:** African language data, multilingual text and speech data, cultural content datasets
- **Funding Sources:** VC-backed including Atlantica Ventures
- **Location:** South Africa
- **Website:** <https://lelapa.ai/about/>
- **Notable Features:** Socially grounded AI research and product lab focused on African languages and contexts. Develops models for low-resource African languages, builds culturally relevant datasets, and collaborates with communities to create inclusive AI tools.

Lithuanian Data Archive for Humanities and Social Sciences (LiDA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Social survey data, historical statistics, political and media data
- **Funding Sources:** Research Council of Lithuania
- **Location:** Lithuania
- **Website:** <https://lida.dataverse.lt/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; curates international survey data

Masakhane

- **Primary Functions:** Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Voice recordings
- **Funding Sources:** Collaborative research and NGO partnerships
- **Location:** Multiple African countries
- **Website:** <https://www.masakhane.io/home>
- **Notable Features:** Advances multilingual NLP in African languages through grassroots open science

MedChain

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Clinical, IoT data, metadata
- **Funding Sources:** Private investment and partnerships
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.medchain.pro/>
- **Notable Features:** Blockchain-based platform for patient-controlled medical data; smart contract-enabled access and digital identities

MIDATA Cooperative

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision, Research
- **Data Types:** Medical records, wearables, genomic, mHealth data
- **Funding Sources:** Grants, university and healthcare partnerships
- **Location:** Switzerland
- **Website:** <http://www.midata.coop>

- **Notable Features:** Citizen-owned health data platform supporting open innovation and app-based research

MIT Laboratory for Social Machines (LSM)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Social media, public discourse, network dynamics
- **Funding Sources:** Twitter (\$10M initial commitment)
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.media.mit.edu/groups/social-machines/overview>
- **Notable Features:** Analyzes large-scale social media, develops tools for mapping discourse and the spread of misinformation and civic engagement platforms to facilitate constructive communication

Murray Research Archive Dataverse (Harvard University)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Preservation

- **Data Types:** Quantitative and qualitative research data, including interview notes, numerical, video, and audio data

- **Funding Sources:** Harvard University (endowed)

- **Location:** United States

- **Website:**

<https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataverse/mra>

- **Notable Features:** Repository for long-term preservation; over 125 TB of research data

N/LAB (Neo-demographic Laboratory for Analytics in Business)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Consumer behavior data from loyalty card transactions; Mobility data
- **Funding Sources:** Funded by UKRI through the ESRC
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.nlab.org.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** Develops ML methods for behavioral data; Conducts social good research; Provides teaching and visualization facilities; Collaborates with industry on anonymized data access

National Neighborhood Indicators Partnership (NNIP)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Neighborhood indicators; Administrative, education, economic, health data
- **Funding Sources:** Annie E. Casey Foundation
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.neighborhoodindicators.org/#1>
- **Notable Features:** Maintains neighborhood-level data; Supports local organizations; Peer-learning network

Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Social science, education, administrative data
- **Funding Sources:** Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research
- **Location:** Norway
- **Website:** <https://sikt.no/en/home>

- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Offers data access, archiving, and training for researchers

Odum Institute Archive Dataverse

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Capacity building, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social science survey data, Harris Polls, U.S. Census data, national statistics, metadata
- **Funding Sources:** University of North Carolina
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://odum.unc.edu/archive/>
- **Notable Features:** One of the largest social science data archives in the U.S.; hosts 50+ years of curated datasets

Open Data Institute (ODI) – Secondary Use of Health Data Project

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** EHRs; Insurance claims; Registries; Clinical trials; Survey data
- **Funding Sources:** Commissioned by Roche

- **Location:** Europe
- **Website:** <https://secondary-use-health-data.theodi.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Assesses and benchmarks policy readiness; Interactive tools to compare policies; Best practice dissemination

OurBrainBank

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity building, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Patient-reported outcomes; Symptoms; QoL metrics; Demographic data
- **Funding Sources:**
- **Location:** US and UK
- **Website:** <https://www.ourbrainbank.org/>
- **Notable Features:** App for tracking glioblastoma symptoms; Shares anonymized data; Advocates patient care

PatientsLikeMe

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Patient-reported data across 2,800+ conditions; Crowdsourced health data
- **Funding Sources:** Initially venture-funded; acquired by Optum Ventures
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://www.patientslikeme.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Platform for peer support; Research collaborations; 850K+ members

Population Research UK (PRUK)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Longitudinal population studies data
- **Funding Sources:** ESRC and MRC
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://pruk.ac.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** Enhances data access/linkage; Supports longitudinal research ecosystem

Portuguese Social Information Archive (APIS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Service Provision
- **Data Types:** Sociopolitical attitudes, values, behaviors, social science research data
- **Funding Sources:** FCT (Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology)
- **Location:** Portugal
- **Website:** <http://www.apis.ics.ulisboa.pt/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Supports secondary use and teaching

PROGEDO Research Infrastructure

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Quantitative social science, survey, longitudinal data
- **Funding Sources:** French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, CNRS
- **Location:** France
- **Website:** <https://www.progedo.fr/>

- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Promotes data reuse and survey participation

Project Data Sphere

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** De-identified cancer trial data; Comparator/control-arm data
- **Funding Sources:** Funded through contributions from member organizations of the CEO Roundtable on Cancer
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <http://www.projectdatasphere.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Open-access oncology platform; Anonymized data from 150+ studies

Pulse Lab Jakarta – Immunization Insights

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Social media data
- **Funding Sources:** UN Global Pulse, Government of Indonesia, UNICEF, WHO
- **Location:** Indonesia

- **Website:** <https://datacollaboratives.org/cases/pulse-lab-jakarta-immunization-insights.html>
- **Notable Features:** Analyzed 88K+ tweets on immunization; Informed immunization campaigns; developed advocacy guidelines

SalusCoop

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Clinical records; Socio-economic data; Lifestyle information
- **Funding Sources:** Collaborations with research and health orgs and programs like Santander X Global Challenge
- **Location:** Spain
- **Website:** <http://www.saluscoop.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Citizen-led data control platform; simplified data donation process through mobile apps, validates and scales citizen science projects

Slovak Archive of Social Data (SASD)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Service Provision
- **Data Types:** Sociological survey data, international comparative surveys (ISSP, ESS, EVS)
- **Funding Sources:** Slovak Ministry of Education, Slovak Academy of Sciences
- **Location:** Slovakia
- **Website:** <https://sasd.sav.sk/sk/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node

Smart Data Donation Service

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Video game data; Social media activity; Online shopping behavior
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.york.ac.uk/news-and-events/news/2024/research/smart-data-donation-service/>

- **Notable Features:** Secure online data donation; Supports research on digital wellbeing

Smart Data Foundry

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research
- **Data Types:** Fintech data, synthetic data, public sector data, data from private sector partnerships
- **Funding Sources:** Wholly owned subsidiary of the University of Edinburgh; registered as a private limited company in Scotland
- **Location:** Scotland
- **Website:** <https://smartdatafoundry.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Enables researcher access to private financial data; Publishes data dashboards, analysis reports, and case studies to support public and policy use; Data access provided through a Trusted Research Environment

Smart Energy Data Service

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Research
- **Data Types:** Data from power networks, energy meters, electric vehicles (EVs); Socio-economic indicators linked to energy consumption and access
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI's Smart Data Research UK
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.sdruk.ukri.org/2025/01/20/new-financial-and-energy-data-services/>
- **Notable Features:** Integrates energy consumption and generation data with social and economic indicators; Supports research into household energy demand, energy poverty, and net-zero transitions; Helps policymakers identify regional needs and develop targeted energy strategies

Social Data Science Alliance

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Platform data from Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs); Digital services and content consumption data; Health, education, and financial data regulated under the EU's Digital Services Act (DSA)
- **Funding Sources:** Supported by Forum on Information and Democracy, DSA40 Data Access Collaboratory, FARI
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://social-data-science-alliance.org/>
- **Notable Features:** Operationalize research aligning with the EU's Digital Services Act (DSA); Conduct audits to ensure initiatives align with the DSA; Research risks associated with Very Large Online Platforms

Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive (SODHA)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service Provision, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social science and digital humanities data

- **Funding Sources:** Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO)
- **Location:** Belgium
- **Website:** <https://www.sodha.be/>
- **Notable Features:** Belgian CESSDA node; long-term archival with access controls

Social Determinants Data Community of Practice (DSSD CoP)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Social determinants of health data across Sub-Saharan Africa
- **Funding Sources:** National Institutes of Health (NIH); led by NYU, Moi University, Brown University
- **Location:** Kenya, United States
- **Website:** nyu-moi-dssd.squarespace.com/cop
- **Notable Features:** Community-driven data indexing initiative; living index of SDoH datasets; focus on contextualized, equity-driven modeling

Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Service Provision
- **Data Types:** Survey and sociological research data
- **Funding Sources:** Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport; Slovenian Research Agency
- **Location:** Slovenia
- **Website:** <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node

SOMAR - Social Media Archive by ICPSR

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social media data
- **Funding Sources:** Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research at the University of Michigan Institute for Social Research
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://socialmediaarchive.org/?ln=en>
- **Notable Features:** Provides researchers access to public and approved secure social media data

So.Da.Net – Greek Research Infrastructure for the Social Sciences

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Capacity Building
- **Data Types:** Social science survey and metadata
- **Funding Sources:** Greek National Road Map for Research Infrastructures
- **Location:** Greece
- **Website:** <https://sodanet.gr/>
- **Notable Features:** Greek CESSDA node; provides e-learning on data use and methodology

Swedish National Data Service (SND)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation, Service Provision
- **Data Types:** Research data across disciplines
- **Funding Sources:** Swedish Research Council; Swedish universities
- **Location:** Sweden
- **Website:** <https://snd.se/en>

- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; Hosts Swiss Household Panel and European surveys; offers survey tools and consulting

Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Service Provision, Preservation
- **Data Types:** National and international survey data
- **Funding Sources:** Swiss universities, national research funding
- **Location:** Switzerland
- **Website:** <https://forscenter.ch>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node

Tanzania Data Lab (dLab)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Official statistics, crowdsourced, geospatial, social media data
- **Funding Sources:** Initially funded by PEPFAR and MCC under the DCLI program
- **Location:** Tanzania

- **Website:** <https://dlab.or.tz>

- **Notable Features:** Provides training in data literacy, offers data services, supports local data-driven innovation and community engagement

Tárki Data Archive

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Social behavior, labor market, income, gender, political behavior data
- **Funding Sources:** Tárki Foundation (nonprofit)
- **Location:** Hungary
- **Website:** <https://www.tarki.hu/eng>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node

The Alan Turing Institute

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Capacity building
- **Data Types:**
- **Funding Sources:** Funded by UKRI through the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)
- **Location:** United Kingdom

- **Website:** <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/interest-groups/novel-data-linkages-health-and-wellbeing>
- **Notable Features:** Research and collaboration on data science, AI; Runs workshops on digital footprints and novel data linkages in health and wellbeing

The Mobility Science Lab

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research
- **Data Types:** Mobility data
- **Funding Sources:** HASP funded by ESRC (2025–2029)
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://mobscilab.com/projects/hasp/>
- **Notable Features:** University Institute Lab; Hosts the Healthy and Sustainable Places Data Service; builds on CDRC's work

UK Biobank

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Grant giving, Preservation
- **Data Types:** De-identified genetic, biological, and medical data; crowdsourced health data from 500,000 UK participants
- **Funding Sources:** Wellcome Trust, Medical Research Council (MRC), Department of Health, Scottish Government, Northwest Regional Development Agency
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** De-identified health data from 500,000 UK participants; Enables health research through approved access; Significant medical research contributions

UK Data Service (UKDS)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Research, Service Provision, Preservation
- **Data Types:** Government surveys, census, business microdata, qualitative studies
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI – ESRC

- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:** <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>
- **Notable Features:** National CESSDA node; UK's largest collection of social/economic research data; training and data discovery support

UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration (UK LLC)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure
- **Data Types:** Links environmental and spatial datasets to traditional longitudinal studies
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI, MRC, ESRC
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:**
<https://www.sdruk.ukri.org/2024/12/03/a-new-frontier-for-population-studies/>
- **Notable Features:** Links environmental data to longitudinal studies; Operates within a Trusted Research Environment; Follows UK Data Service's Five Safes Framework

United Kingdom Research and Innovation's Smart Data Research UK (SDRUK)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building, Grant giving
- **Data Types:** Diverse
- **Funding Sources:** UKRI Infrastructure Fund
- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:**
<https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-area-of-investment-and-support/smart-data-research-uk/>
- **Notable Features:** Supports development of data services; Offers accelerator programme

University of Liverpool's Geographic Data Science Lab (GDSDL)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Spatial data on urban environments, population dynamics, housing and infrastructure; Geographic indicators of inequality and regional change
- **Funding Sources:** SDRUK

- **Location:** United Kingdom
- **Website:**
<https://news.liverpool.ac.uk/2024/10/17/double-success-for-gdsl-in-latest-smart-data-research-programme/>;
<https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/geographic-data-science/>
- **Notable Features:** A research and teaching centre at the intersection of Geographic Information Science, Spatial Analysis and Applied Geocomputation; Leads Smart Data Research UK-funded services related to geographic and infrastructure data

Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC)

- **Primary Functions:** Research, Data and Infrastructure, Capacity building
- **Data Types:** Transport and mobility; Housing and property; Labour market; Environment
- **Funding Sources:** Funded by: UKRI, SDRUK, University of Glasgow
- **Location:** Scotland
- **Website:** <https://www.ubdc.ac.uk/>

- **Notable Features:** Provides open-access datasets and safeguarded datasets under controlled access; Conducts interdisciplinary research using smart and traditional data

Ushahidi

- **Primary Functions:** Service provision, Research, Data and Infrastructure
- **Data Types:** Crowdsourced reports (e.g. crisis events, rights violations, election monitoring); crowdsourced geospatial data
- **Funding Sources:** Grants from Humanity United, MacArthur Foundation, Omidyar Network, Mozilla, EU, and others
- **Location:** Kenya
- **Website:** <https://www.usshahidi.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Develops open-source tools for data collection and interactive mapping; Supports crisis response, elections, and human rights monitoring globally; Deployed over 100,000 times in 159+ countries

Strava Metro (Strava Labs)

- **Primary Functions:** Data and Infrastructure, Service provision
- **Data Types:** Aggregated and anonymized mobility data
- **Funding Sources:** Strava Inc.
- **Location:** United States
- **Website:** <https://labs.strava.com/>
- **Notable Features:** Provides aggregated GPS data from Strava users to improve infrastructure and transportation planning